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SSD2 coding of the food and feed samples tested in the frame of the pesticide residue monitoring under Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 and their analytical results

(2018 data collection)

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

Abstract

The present document provides working instructions and guidance on how to use the SSD2 data model to code the food samples taken and the analytical results of the control activities carried out in 2018 in the EU regarding pesticide residues in food and feed under Regulation (EC) No 396/2005. This document does not replace – but it complements - the general EFSA Guidance on SSD2 and the EFSA Guidelines on Harmonised Chemical Reporting. It is meant to provide guidance on specific technical and legislative aspects related to pesticide residue monitoring in food and feed samples. This document will be updated for the reporting of pesticide residue data that will be generated from 2019 onwards, when EFSA will only collect data in SSD2 and no longer in SSD1.

Key words: Pesticides, residue, food, monitoring, coding, SSD2, MTX, FoodEx2

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1. Introduction

In 2013, EFSA published a revision on Standard Sample Description (SSD2) (EFSA, 2013), which provides the data specification for reporting laboratory results in samples from the food chain¹. This version incorporates FoodEx2 (EFSA, 2015), a food description system which allows detailed classification of simple and complex food items and which is compatible with the EU Menu food consumption surveys (EFSA, 2014).

Data providers have been requested to modify their data management tools from SSD1 to SSD2 and to implement the SSD2 format. Since the reporting in 2018 of the 2017 pesticide monitoring data, the Member States have the possibility to code their results on the control activities in SSD1 or SSD2 format. In 2020, the 2019 pesticide residue monitoring data will be only transmitted to EFSA in SSD2 format.

The focus of this document is put on the SSD data elements that shall be reported on a mandatory basis in the frame of the pesticide residue monitoring data collection, related to specific information of the pesticide residues area and required for the preparation of EU annual reports on pesticide residues in food (including the information to perform the assessment of the dietary consumer's risk due to pesticide residues in food).

Thus, this document intends to provide specific guidelines in the area of pesticide residues and to increase the data quality on certain SSD variables. In particular, the content of this document is meant to highlight the necessary information for reporting SSD2 data elements, which are new compared to SSD1, such as the data element *sampMatCode* that represents the major change and describes the food samples by means of the FoodEx2 system. Other SSD2 elements than the ones described in this document (not mandatory SSD data elements) can be reported at the discretion of the data provider.

2. Background

Compared to SSD1, the SSD2 includes updated lists of standardised data elements and has been modified to fully support the FoodEx2 food classification and description system.

As SSD1, the logical model SSD2 is comprised of a combination of three main components/groups of terms and characteristics:

1. Data elements definition and structure
2. Controlled terminologies (catalogues)
3. Business Rules (BR) to ensure the validity and/or consistency of the information provided

The directions given in the present document only apply and are specific for reporting the results of the control activities carried out in the frame of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 on pesticide residues in food in 2018. This document also provides guidelines on the compatibility and correspondences between the two SSD versions and the mapping from SSD1 to SSD2 related to specific data elements and catalogues.

The main changes introduced by SSD2 compared to SSD1 are here below briefly highlighted.

Data elements definition and structure

- SSD2 encompasses more data elements than SSD1; however, many of the new data fields in SSD2 are not necessary or applicable to the pesticide monitoring data collection. For example, the elements coded I.01 to I.04 on the *Isolate* 'addresses the reporting of the isolate-based data on antimicrobial resistance (see Table 1);
- Some SSD data elements' names changed from SSD1 to SSD2, but their meaning remained unchanged (see the text reported in **bold** in the second column in Table 2);
- Some SSD1 data elements have been 'aggregated' in single SSD2 elements; for example, the three SSD1 elements describing the food sample tested (*prodCode*, *prodTreat* and

¹ SSD2 Description and Guidance Document available at: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/3424>

prodProdMeth in SSD1) have been aggregated into one single SSD2 element (*sampMatCode*) (see Table 2, line for 'E.02');

- SSD2 maintains the conceptual structure of SSD1 and is back-compatible, from a content perspective, with the previous version (SSD1). The contrary is not possible due to the introduction of repeatable and compound data elements and the implementation of the 'FoodEx2' (see Section 3.3.3).

The SSD2 data elements are organised in 14 different groups of elements, being the elements in each group referring to the same type of information; each element belonging to the same group has been given a code (e.g. 'A' in the element code 'A.01'=local organisation identification), which starts with the same letter (see column 'SSD2 element code' in Table 2 **Error! Reference source not found.**). The 14 groups of SSD2 data elements are briefly outlined below (Table 1).

Table 1: List of all SSD2 data elements groups and their relevance for the pesticide residue monitoring data collection

SSD2 data element group	Type of information	Short explanation and/or examples of information	Relevance for the reporting of pesticide residues data
A	Local organisation	Information on the organisation (e.g. the national competent authority) that initially requested or performed the sampling and is responsible for the implementation of the sampling programme.	Yes
B	Sampling programme	The description of criteria, purpose, method or legislative reference used to generate a sampling event (e.g. the sampling strategy, sampling method and the programme legal reference).	Yes
C	Sampling event	The sampling event represents the aggregate of all samples taken at a certain time to investigate chemical or microbiological properties of the sampling unit under consideration at a certain time.	No
D	Sample taken	Details of the samples taken such as the unique sampling Identification code, the sampling date, and the name of the reporting country.	Yes
E	Matrix sampled	The description of the item sampled and of its relevant characteristics available before the analysis. For example, the description of the food product, its industrial processing and the production method.	Yes
F	Sample analysed	The 'sample analysed' is usually, but not always, identical to the 'sample taken', i.e. with the sample sent to the laboratory. This information is not necessary for the pesticide residue data reporting, except for the information on the date of analysis.	No (except for the 'Year of analysis')
G	Matrix analysed	Description of the 'matrix analysed' will often be the same as the 'matrix sampled'. This section allows the inclusion of an additional encoded and textual description of the 'matrix analysed'.	No
H	Sample analysed portion	The 'sample analysed portion' (often called 'test portion') is a replicate achieved by subdividing the sample analysed. The usage of SSD element 'sample analysed portion' is only needed when an explicit requirement in a data collection domain exists to report the results of these replicas; this is not the case for the pesticide residue areas as per the EC Guidelines on analytical quality control (EC, 2017) ² .	No
I	Isolate	The isolate identifies, by a unique code, a culture of a biological agent, isolated from a specific 'sample taken'. Thus, not applicable for the pesticide residue area.	No
J	Laboratory	The laboratory in which the analysis was performed or the laboratory responsible for the results. Information such as the lab ID and the lab accreditation status are needed.	Yes
K	Parameter	The specification of the parameter (analyte) determined in the matrix analysed, e.g. the <i>paramCode</i> and <i>paramType</i> .	Yes

² Document also available at: https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/plant/docs/pesticides_mrl_guidelines_wrkdoc_2017-11813.pdf

SSD2 data element group	Type of information	Short explanation and/or examples of information	Relevance for the reporting of pesticide residues data
L	Analytical method	The laboratory method of analysis and diagnostic method used to generate the result. At the moment, this information is not compulsory for the pesticide residue data reporting.	No
M	Result	The result of the laboratory tests, as a quantitative or qualitative outcome value. Information relating to the result also includes the accreditation procedure, limits of detection and quantification and the result value for the analytical method (e.g. <i>resLOQ</i> , <i>resType</i> and <i>resVal</i>).	Yes
N	Evaluation:	Assessment of the result, evaluating its compliance with a defined limit (e.g. the result evaluation data element <i>evalCode</i>).	Yes

Controlled terminologies (catalogues)

- SSD2 foresees only one new catalogue for an SSD data element, i.e. the MTX catalogue of the FoodEx2 classification system; this catalogue incorporates the coded information previously listed separately in three SSD1 catalogues (MATRIX, PRODTR and PROMD). Otherwise, the catalogues used in SSD1 are the same as the ones for data coding in SSD2.
- A first FoodEx2 maintenance was carried out in 2015 and a second during the years 2016-2018 in order to evaluate further comments and proposals provided to EFSA by users and stakeholders. Information on the maintenance of this system can be read in the dedicated EFSA technical report (EFSA, 2019a)³.
- SSD2 allows 'simple' and 'repeatable' data elements; the simple elements can contain only one 'element value' which may be either a 'text', a 'numeric' or a 'catalogue' value (e.g. the sample identification code chosen by the laboratory, a numerical value expressed in mg/kg for a quantified pesticide residue or a code selected from the catalogue for indicating the sampling country); instead, the 'repeatable' elements may contain one or more values (an example could be the reporting of more than one action taken code in case of a sample non-compliant with the legal limit). Furthermore, 'compound' data elements are possible in SSD2; this type of elements may contain one or several 'simple' elements, which are named 'attributes' or the 'compound element' and where each attribute can have values that can be text, numerical or catalogue/code values (e.g. the SSD2 data element E.02 'sampMatCode', which describes through attributes the raw food product tested (one attribute) and the related product treatment (the second attribute). Explanations on these features are provided elsewhere (EFSA, 2013).

Business Rules

- The SSD1 Business Rules (BR) have been adapted to the SSD2 data elements, 'translating' the logical checks and the error description into new statements that are more compatible with SSD2; this applies to both general BR (that are applicable to all food domains data collections in EFSA) and BR specific for the pesticide residue monitoring. Compared to the SSD1 BR for the 2018 pesticide residue data collection, the SSD2 BR foresee additional data validation checks as indicated in paragraph 3.4.
- The list of BR is provided in a separate document.

2.1. Additional information

The reader not familiar with SSD2 and with FoodEx2 is warmly recommended to read the reference documents available (EFSA, 2013; EFSA, 2015).

³ Document available also on-line at: <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1584>

All the resources mentioned and related to this document (structural metadata, catalogues, business rules, schema definitions) are published in Knowledge Junction in machine readable format and human readable, where appropriate⁴.

3. Data and Methodologies

3.1. SSD2

Compared to SSD1, the SSD2 introduced for the pesticide residue area three major changes:

- SSD2 uses a more complete sample identification approach based on four levels (sampling event identification, sample taken identification, sample analysed identification, sample analysed portion sequence). However, for the pesticide area only one level of sample identification will be needed;
- FoodEx2 provides a greater level of details, which was not available in the former MATRIX classification system. Although a mapping algorithm to transform MATRIX codes in FoodEx2 codes exists, users are recommended to re-check their mapping procedures to ensure the mappings are providing accurate transformations;
- FoodEx2 includes as facets some SSD1 fields that are mandatory for some data collection such as pesticides monitoring results, e.g. information on the organic method of production *prodProdMeth* ('Method of production' data element and PRODMD catalogue in SSD1) versus the facet F21 'Production-method' catalogue in FoodEx2 as well as information on the industrial processing of samples *prodTreat* ('Product treatment' and PRODTR catalogue in SSD1) versus the facet F28 'Process' catalogue in FoodEx2 (see Figure 1). While mapping from the PRODMD catalogue to the corresponding FoodEx2 facet (F21, 'Production-method' facet) is simple, mapping from the PRODTR catalogue to the corresponding FoodEx2 facet (F28 'Process') is not trivial;

Figure 1: Mapping of the three main SSD1 data elements and related catalogues to the SSD2 food descriptor *sampMatCode* and its MTX catalogue

- In general, the variables relevant for pesticide residues area have been transferred without change from SSD1 to SSD2. In some cases, variables and catalogues have been given new names to enhance the clarity and consistency of the data model especially where these fields interact with the new needs for SSD2 (e.g. extension to food domains other than the pesticide residue data collection).

⁴ EFSA SSD Catalogue Browser User Guide available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1407102>; Web link to download the Catalogue Browser: <https://github.com/openefsa/catalogue-browser/wiki>

This creates a need for existing national systems to revise some SSD variable names and the order of elements in the XML-files to be transmitted to EFSA;

- In some cases, catalogues and variables have been set up to handle 'compound' type elements⁵ (see in column 'Element Type' of Table 2 the concerned data elements/catalogues); handling of such changes will also have to be implemented at national level.

3.2. SSD2 data elements

SSD2 is made up of 95 data elements. Compared to SSD1, the name and meaning of almost the totality of these elements has remained unchanged. Some of the SSD2 are new, i.e. have been introduced to report new pieces of information not reportable in SSD1.

Table 2 provides for the full list of SSD2 data elements and their correspondence to the SSD1 elements, where appropriate:

- SSD2 data elements whose names are reported in **bold** refer to elements for which a change in their name occurred from SSD1 to SSD2;
- SSD2 data elements, which are mandatory in the pesticide monitoring data collection, are flagged as 'Mandatory' in the last column of the table;
- SSD1 data elements that are aggregated into one single SSD2 elements can be identified in the last column of the table (i.e. in column 'SSD1 Element Name' where more than one SSD1 element is reported);
- New SSD2 data elements that were not foreseen in SSD1 have a corresponding blank cell in the last column 'SSD1 Element Name' of the table.

In the context of this document, whenever the name of an SSD data element is stated in the text (whether SSD1 or SSD2 element) it is typed in *italic* font (e.g. the data element *sampMatCode* is entered in the document as *sampMatCode*).

Table 2 also provides for the SSD2 data elements that are considered as 'mandatory' in the frame of the pesticide residue data reporting, but also for the future harmonised chemical reporting⁶. However, it is recalled that the harmonised data collection provisions will not be applicable for the 2018 pesticide monitoring data to be reported to EFSA in 2019.

⁵SSD2 Description and Guidance Document available at: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/3424>

⁶'Chemical Monitoring Reporting Guidelines (SSD2)', document available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/2543211#.XGKdwFxKiUk>

Table 2 List of all SSD2 elements and their mapping to SSD1: mandatory SSD2 elements to be reported for the pesticide residue monitoring data collection and in the frame of the future chemical monitoring reporting⁷

SSD2 Element Code	SSD2 Element Name⁸	SSD2 Element Label	Element Type⁹	Controlled terminology (catalogue)	Mandatory element for the pesticide residues and/or for the harmonised chemical reporting¹⁰	SSD1 Element Name
A.01	<i>localOrgId</i>	Local organisation identification code				<i>localOrgId</i>
A.02	<i>localOrgCountry</i>	Local organisation country		COUNTRY		<i>localOrgCountry</i>
A.03	<i>localOrgInfo</i>	Local organisation additional information	Compound type			
B.01	<i>progId</i>	Sampling programme identification code			Mandatory only for the future harmonised data collection	<i>progCode</i>
B.02	<i>progLegalRef</i>	Programme legal reference		LEGREF	Mandatory	<i>progLegalRef</i>
B.03	<i>sampStrategy</i>	Sampling strategy		SAMPSTR	Mandatory	<i>progSampStrategy</i>
B.04	<i>progType</i>	Programme type		PRGTYP	Mandatory	<i>progType</i>
B.05	<i>sampMethod</i>	Sampling method		SAMPMD	Mandatory	<i>sampMethod</i>
B.06	<i>sampler</i>	Sampler		SAMPLR	Mandatory only for the future harmonised data collection	
B.07	<i>sampPoint</i>	Sampling point		SAMPNT	Mandatory	<i>sampPoint</i>
B.08	<i>progInfo</i>	Additional sampling program information	Compound type			
C.01	<i>sampEventId</i>	Sampling event identification code				
C.02	<i>sampUnitType</i>	Sampling unit type		SAMPUNTYP		

⁷ The Mandatory data elements to be reported for the future Harmonised Chemical Monitoring are published in the EFSA document 'Chemical Monitoring Reporting Guidelines (SSD2)'; document available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/2543211#.XGKdwFxKiUk>. It should be noted that the directions given in the latter Guidelines are not applicable for the 2018 pesticide monitoring data collection; they will only apply starting from the pesticide data collection referring to the monitoring year 2019 forward.

⁸ The SSD2 data elements' names reported in bold characters in this column refer to element names that changed from SSD1 to SSD2; the corresponding SSD1 element names are reported in the last column of the table

⁹ The definition of 'Compound' and 'Repeatable' type of elements is provided in SSD2 Guidance Document available at: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/3424>

¹⁰ The data elements flagged as 'Mandatory' refer to the elements that are compulsory for the pesticide residue data collection; the cells referring to these elements are filled in grey colour in the table; these pesticide mandatory data elements could also be mandatory for the harmonised chemical reporting. The elements indicated as 'Mandatory only for the future harmonised data collection' are not compulsory for the 2018 pesticide monitoring data collection.

SSD2 Element Code	SSD2 Element Name⁸	SSD2 Element Label	Element Type⁹	Controlled terminology (catalogue)	Mandatory element for the pesticide residues and/or for the harmonised chemical reporting¹⁰	SSD1 Element Name
C.03	sampUnitSize	Sampling unit size				lotSize
C.04	sampUnitSizeUnit	Sampling unit size unit		UNIT		lotSizeUnit
C.05	sampUnitIds	Other sampling unit identifications	Compound type			
C.06	sampEventInfo	Additional sampling event information	Compound type			
D.01	sampId	Sample taken identification code			Mandatory	labSampCode
D.02	repCountry	Reporting country		COUNTRY		
D.03	sampCountry	Country of sampling		COUNTRY	Mandatory	sampCountry
D.04	sampArea	Area of sampling		NUTS		sampArea
D.05	repYear	Reporting year				
D.06	sampY	Year of sampling			Mandatory	sampY
D.07	sampM	Month of sampling			Mandatory	sampM
D.08	sampD	Day of sampling			Mandatory	sampD
D.09	sampSize	Sample taken size				
D.10	sampSizeUnit	Sample taken size unit		UNIT		
D.11	sampInfo.OrigSampId	Additional Sample taken information				
E.01	sampMatType	Type of matrix		MTXTYP		
E.02	sampMatCode	Coded description of the matrix of the sample taken	Compound type	MATRIX (SSD1)/MTX of FoodEx2 (SSD2)	Mandatory	prodCode, prodProdMeth, prodPack, prodTreat, prodIngrid
E.03	sampMatText	Text description of the matrix of the sample taken				prodText
E.04	origCountry	Country of origin of the sample taken		COUNTRY	Mandatory	origCountry
E.05	origArea	Area of origin of the sample taken		NUTS		origArea
E.06	origFishAreaCode	Area of origin for fisheries or aquaculture activities code of the sample taken		FAREA		origFishAreaCode
E.07	origFishAreaText	Area of origin for fisheries or aquaculture activities text of the sample taken				origFishAreaText

SSD2 Element Code	SSD2 Element Name⁸	SSD2 Element Label	Element Type⁹	Controlled terminology (catalogue)	Mandatory element for the pesticide residues and/or for the harmonised chemical reporting¹⁰	SSD1 Element Name
E.08	<i>procCountry</i>	Country of processing of the sample taken		COUNTRY		<i>procCountry</i>
E.09	<i>procArea</i>	Area of processing of the sample taken		NUTS		<i>procArea</i>
E.10	sampMatInfo	Additional information on the matrix sampled	Compound type			<i>prodCom, prodD, prodM, prodY, expiryD, expiryM, prodManuf, prodBrandName</i>
F.01	<i>sampAnId</i>	Sample analysed identification code				
F.02	<i>sampAnRefTime</i>	Sample analysis reference time		REFTM		
F.03	<i>analysisY</i>	Year of analysis			Mandatory	<i>analysisY</i>
F.04	<i>analysisM</i>	Month of analysis				<i>analysisM</i>
F.05	<i>analysisD</i>	Day of analysis				<i>analysisD</i>
F.06	<i>sampAnInfo</i>	Additional information on the sample analysed	Compound type			
G.01	<i>anMatCode</i>	Coded description of the analysed matrix	Compound type	MTX of FoodEx2 (SSD2)		
G.02	<i>anMatText</i>	Text description of the matrix analysed				
G.03	<i>anMatInfo</i>	Additional information on the analysed matrix	Compound type			
H.01	anPortSeq	Sample analysed portion sequence				<i>labSubSampCode</i>
H.02	<i>anPortSize</i>	Sample analysed portion size				
H.03	<i>anPortSizeUnit</i>	Sample analysed portion size unit		UNIT		
H.04	<i>anPortInfo</i>	Additional information on the sample analysed portion	Compound type			
I.01	<i>isolId</i>	Isolate identification				
I.02	<i>isolParamCode</i>	Coded description of the isolate	Compound type	PARAM		
I.03	<i>isolParamText</i>	Text description of the isolate				
I.04	<i>isolInfo</i>	Additional information on the isolate	Compound type			
J.01	labId	Laboratory identification code			Mandatory	<i>labCode</i>
J.02	<i>labAccred</i>	Laboratory accreditation		LABACC	Mandatory	<i>labAccred</i>

SSD2 Element Code	SSD2 Element Name⁸	SSD2 Element Label	Element Type⁹	Controlled terminology (catalogue)	Mandatory element for the pesticide residues and/or for the harmonised chemical reporting¹⁰	SSD1 Element Name
J.03	<i>labCountry</i>	Laboratory country		COUNTRY	Mandatory only for the future harmonised data collection	<i>labCountry</i>
J.04	<i>labInfo</i>	Additional information on the laboratory	Compound type			
K.01	<i>paramType</i>	Type of parameter		PARAMTYP	Mandatory	<i>paramType</i>
K.02	<i>paramCode</i>	Coded description of the parameter	Compound type	PARAM	Mandatory	<i>paramCode</i>
K.03	<i>paramText</i>	Parameter text				<i>paramText</i>
L.01	<i>anMethRefId</i>	Analytical method identification			Mandatory only for the future harmonised data collection	<i>anMethRefCode</i>
L.02	<i>anMethRef Code</i>	Analytical method reference code		ANLYREFMD		
L.03	<i>anMethType</i>	Analytical method type		ANLYTYP	Mandatory only for the future harmonised data collection	
L.04	<i>anMethCode</i>	Analytical method code	Compound type	ANLYMD	Mandatory only for the future harmonised data collection	<i>anMethCode</i>
L.05	<i>anMethText</i>	Analytical method text				<i>anMethText</i>
L.06	<i>anMethInfo</i>	Additional information on the analytical method	Compound type			
M.01	<i>resId</i>	Result identification code			Mandatory	<i>resultCode</i>
M.02	<i>accredProc</i>	Accreditation procedure for the analytical method		MDACC	Mandatory only for the future harmonised data collection	<i>accredProc</i>
M.03	<i>resUnit</i>	Result unit		UNIT	Mandatory	<i>resUnit</i>
M.04	<i>resLOD</i>	Result LOD				<i>resLOD</i>
M.05	<i>resLOQ</i>	Result LOQ			Mandatory	<i>resLOQ</i>
M.06	<i>resLLWR</i>	Result lower limit of the working range				
M.07	<i>resULWR</i>	Result upper limit of the working range				<i>CCalpha</i>
M.08	<i>CCalpha</i>	CC alpha				<i>CCbeta</i>
M.09	<i>CCbeta</i>	CC beta				
M.10	<i>resVal</i>	Result value			Mandatory only under certain conditions	<i>resVal</i>

SSD2 Element Code	SSD2 Element Name⁸	SSD2 Element Label	Element Type⁹	Controlled terminology (catalogue)	Mandatory element for the pesticide residues and/or for the harmonised chemical reporting¹⁰	SSD1 Element Name
M.11	<i>resValRec</i>	Result value recovery rate			Mandatory only under certain conditions	<i>resValRec</i>
M.12	<i>resValRecCorr</i>	Result value corrected for recovery		YESNO		<i>resValRecCorr</i>
M.13	exprResPerc	Expression of result percentage	Compound type			<i>moistPerc, fatPerc</i>
M.14	exprResType	Expression of result type		EXPRRES		<i>exprRes</i>
M.15	<i>resQualValue</i>	Result qualitative value		POSNEG	Mandatory only under certain conditions	<i>resQualValue</i>
M.16	<i>resType</i>	Type of result		VALTYP	Mandatory	<i>resType</i>
M.17	<i>resValUncert</i>	Result value uncertainty				<i>resValUncert</i>
M.18	<i>resValUncertSD</i>	Result value uncertainty Standard deviation				<i>resValUncertSD</i>
M.19	<i>resRefId</i>	Result reference identification				
M.20	resInfo.notSummed	Indicates LOQ should be calculated during the submission process	Compound type	YESNO		<i>resComm</i>
N.01	evalLowLimit	Limit for the result evaluation			Mandatory only under certain conditions	<i>resLegalLimit</i>
N.02	<i>evalHighLimit</i>	Limit for the result evaluation (High limit)				
N.03	evalLimitType	Type of limit for the result evaluation		LMTTYP		<i>resLegalLimitType</i>
N.04	evalCode	Evaluation of the result		RESEVAL	Mandatory	<i>resEvaluation</i>
N.05	<i>actTakenCode</i>	Action Taken		ACTION		<i>actTakenCode</i>
N.06	<i>evalInfo.conclusion</i>	Conclusion of follow-up investigation		CONCLUS		
N.06	<i>evalInfo.com</i>	Comment				

3.3. FoodEx2 and Catalogue Browser

The main change introduced by moving from SSD1 to SSD2 is represented by the FoodEx2 (EFSA, 2015)¹¹.

FoodEx2 is a comprehensive, descriptive food classification and description system developed and maintained in EFSA for different purposes; it makes use of common language and – at the moment – its content is available in English only.

The Catalogue Browser is an application developed by EFSA which allows to browse, search, analyse and maintain the various SSD catalogues provided by EFSA into the Data Collection Framework (DCF). Each catalogue has different entries which are aggregated within a hierarchical parent-child relationship structure easy to surf. The tool provides also a collection of additional information, called 'facets', which are in few words descriptors for the initially selected record (base-term)¹². Every term into the catalogue is described using common names and dedicated tools will provide support to check the validity of the code selected (e.g. the Interpreting and Checking Tool¹³ (ICT tool)).

As for any other SSD catalogue, the Catalogue Browser is also managing the FoodEx2 classification and its associated MTX catalogue. Thus, the Browser tool allows for the navigation of the FoodEx2 coding system and – where needed - to create new codes.

In order to select the most appropriate food descriptors codes, please install this browser locally on your computer/system. An EFSA's Catalogue browser user guide¹³ is provided by EFSA and the reader is warmly recommended to consult it.

The Browser is available on-line, and it is always updated according to newest released versions of its content. The data providers are invited to always make use of the latest catalogue version available.

The SSD catalogue, which is based on the FoodEx2 system, is named 'MTX'; this catalogue is used to report (and understand the mapping) of the information to be reported in the SSD element *sampMatCode* to the SSD1 elemental information (*prodCode*, *prodTreat* and *prodProdMeth*) (see also **Figure 1**). Thus, from the MTX catalogue it is possible to select the existing codes to describe the following characteristics of the sampled food: the food/matrix sampled (i.e. the food product tested), its industrial processing status (i.e. the food 'product treatment') and the method of production (e.g. if the sample was taken from an organic production lot or not).

The currently existing legislation with specific food classifications and compliance criteria based on these, such as Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 on pesticides residues, are implemented in the FoodEx2 classification and the Catalogue Browser (see also 3.3.1). Thus, the codes applicable to the food items/groups in the pesticide MRL food classification are all reflected in the FoodEx2; in addition to this, the MTX catalogue of the FoodEx2 reflects the sub-codes adopted by the EU food items reported in part B of Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 on the 'Other products to which the same MRLs apply' (as an example please see Example 3 on clementine samples coding).

The pesticide classification food terms (i.e. MATRIX catalogue terms in SSD1) are all included as such in FoodEx2 as Raw Primary Commodities (RPC) and hold the pre-assigned code from the MATRIX catalogue as implicit attribute. In addition, the food items derived from a single RPC are also linked to the pesticide MATRIX code (referred in the Catalogue Browser to the code attribute 'matrixCode', which corresponds to the MATRIX codes with the prefix 'P' but without the suffix 'A' or 'B'). Therefore, a pesticide MATRIX code can be derived from the FoodEx2 code provided.

However, in the case of some composite foods, issues in the mapping can occur since the matrix code might not be unambiguously defined, and the mapping rules are specific for the pesticide monitoring data collection and analysis. For these items, the FoodEx2 code will be linked to the SSD1 MATRIX code 'Not in list' (see section 3.3.3).

¹¹ 'The food classification and description system FoodEx2', document available also at:

<http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/sp.efsa.2015.EN-804/epdf>

¹² Useful information is also available at: <https://github.com/openefsa/catalogue-browser/wiki>

¹³ The ICT Tool explanations are provided in the document 'EFSA's Catalogue browser user guide', document available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/1407103#.XIi1vyhKiUm>

To learn more on the FoodEx2 and to practice its use, the reader is warmly recommended to watch the two related EFSA webinars¹⁴.

3.3.1. FoodEx2 codes selection

The basic food list of FoodEx2 is organised in groups of code terms, which are called 'hierarchies'. The hierarchy to be used to select the terms and codes for the pesticide monitoring results is the '**Reporting**' hierarchy; this hierarchy is also implemented in the FoodEx2 Browser. Codes that are not included in the 'Reporting' hierarchy cannot be selected in the frame of the pesticide monitoring data collection; in case they will be selected by mistake they will be rejected by EFSA during the data validation phase.

The current food classification applicable in the pesticide residue MRL under Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 is fully addressed in the Reporting FoodEx2 hierarchy; thus, all the FoodEx2 terms under this hierarchy will allow the data provider to identify and select the appropriate code for the raw (fresh/frozen) samples analysed (e.g. a raw apple). In addition, in cases where the tested samples refer to a 'processed' (e.g. apple juice) food or to composite food (e.g. pizza), the FoodEx2 should provide all the necessary codes in the MTX catalogue.

However, it should be noted that a few codes that are present in the SSD1 MATRIX catalogue are not available in the 'Reporting' hierarchy of FoodEx2. This is the case for the MATRIX code 'Not in list'. Higher-level food classification codes in the pesticide MRL food classification (e.g. for the MATRIX code P0500000A used for the general food group of 'Cereals') in principle are no longer needed in SSD2 as specific codes that describe all food items are already present in the MTX catalogue. Higher-level codes if present in the 'Reporting' hierarchy are reportable, even though strongly discouraged.

It should be noted that together with 'source' and 'part-nature' facets, the facet 'process' also covers an important role in FoodEx2 since it is of fundamental importance for the reporting of food in the samples analysed for pesticide residues. Whilst the 'source' and 'part-nature' facets are always implicitly completed for each term ('core' and 'extended' terms) of the 'Reporting' hierarchy, the facet for coding the 'process technology' is implicit only for those terms where it can be unambiguously derived by the term name or scope-notes (e.g. the code associated to 'orange juice' implicitly already contains the facet code 'Juicing', see Example 4). More explanation on this topic is provided later in the document, supported by dedicated examples.

To conclude, the FoodEx2/MTX users should be aware that the reporting of generic facet descriptors such as 'Unprocessed' are reportable only to specific data collection domains. Use of more specific facets descriptors is encouraged as this makes their usage possible within multiple data domains (more detail and examples are provided in Section 4.10).

3.3.2. Resolution of overlapping between SSD1 elements and FoodEx2 facets

Since the introduction of FoodEx2 catalogue with the structure of facets, there are some overlap between data elements existing in SSD1 and the information provided by the FoodEx2 facets. The single and distinct data elements *prodCode*, *prodTreat*, *prodProdMethod*, *prodPack* and *prodIngred* were introduced preliminarily in SSD1 since at that time there was no complete, harmonised and systematic food classification system available. The SSD2 data element *sampMatCode* incorporates all the above SSD1 single elements in one unique data variable by using facets.

Considering that some of the above single SSD1 elements are mandatory in some data collection domains (e.g. the SSD1 element *prodTreat* is mandatory for pesticide residues data collection), this reportability condition has been reflected in SSD2, imposing some of the corresponding facets to be mandatory. For facets that are not to be reported on a mandatory basis and that are not reported by the data provider, EFSA assumes by default that a given facet/attribute applies (see Example 3).

¹⁴ Two on-line training/tutorials on the FoodEx2 classification system and practical guidance on its use are available on the EFSA webpage (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/180926>)

Therefore, the data providers should be aware that FoodEx2 defines default values for some facets (implicit facets) for those terms where the facets characteristics can be unambiguously derived by the term definition (e.g. for the code allocated to the 'processed' food 'orange juice'); these facet descriptors can be visualized in the 'scope note' reported in the MTX catalogue and easily readable through the Catalogue Browser.

In principle, the implicit facets do not need to be reported by the data providers, as they are already populated by the system before the automatic check (i.e. the application of the Business Rules) of the mandatory SSD2 facet (corresponding to a mandatory SSD1 data element) is performed.

In very specific cases, the data providers should verify before its data transmission if the mandatory facets are present in a term definition, otherwise the data transmitted to EFSA may be rejected during the data validation (see also the use of facet F20 'part consumed/analysed' for the sample coding in case of mammals and birds meat muscle, Example 9).

Finally, it should be noted that the SSD2 variable *sampMatCode* addresses also two additional food samples characteristics/descriptors that could have been reported in SSD1 through two distinct data elements (see e.g. section 3.3.3.4): *prodPack* and *prodInged*. Since these two SSD1 data variables were rarely reported and were returned only a voluntary basis in the frame of the pesticide monitoring data collection in SSD1 format, their corresponding facets in FoodEx2 are not mandatory as well.

3.3.3. Mapping FoodEx2 to SSD1 coding (e.g. *prodCode*, *prodTreat*, *prodPack* and *prodProdMethod*)

In order for EFSA to validate the coded pesticide monitoring results against the MRL database and the MatrixTool and to perform certain data analysis following data transmission, EFSA has proceeded to the mapping of FoodEx2 codes in SSD2 to the corresponding MATRIX, PRODTR, PRODM, PRODPAC codes in SSD1.

For this purpose, specific FoodEx2 rules (or 'mapping' rules) have been set-up based on a mapping algorithm/procedure specifically created for the reporting of the pesticide monitoring data; the diagram representing this procedure is provided separately (see the Visio diagram 'MatrixMapping'). The data provider will not need the details of the mapping as the recoding is automatically performed by EFSA. However, the mapping is briefly outlined below for information.

For the mapping from FoodEx2 codes into SSD1 data elements, the focus is put on the FoodEx2 facet descriptors F27 ('Source-commodities'), F28 ('Process'), F21 ('Production-method') and F19 ('Packaging-material'), as briefly described in the next sub-paragraphs.

3.3.3.1. *prodCode* of SSD1

A link with the SSD1 food classification system (Matrix) is stored in the *matrixCode* attribute of the FoodEx2 facet F27 ('Source-commodities') for the terms where a correspondence exists. The facet F27 and its *matrixCode* attribute are mapped to the *prodCode* of SSD1. The mapping is executed by selecting the *matrixCode* attribute of the MTX catalogue according to the below steps:

- If there is only one source-commodity reported in the same MTX term (e.g. for the code 'apples'), then the mapping uses its corresponding *matrixCode* attribute;
- If there is more than one source-commodities encoded in the reported MTX term, then the mapping recodes the food to the *prodCode*='Not in list'=XXXXXXA in SSD1; this applies to the composite food samples made-up with more than one 'food items/ingredients' (e.g. pizza);
- If there are no source-commodities, then the recoding selects the *matrixCode* attribute of the MTX base-term;
- Exception case to the above: for 'Food products for young children' and its children terms in the FoodEx2, the mapping follows a different recoding; it uses the *matrixCode* attribute of the MTX base-term disregarding the corresponding source-commodity.

After the above first steps (i.e. the identification of the appropriate matrixCode attribute), the mapping process proceeds with the identification of code of the MATRIX catalogue to map to:

- If the value of the attribute matrixCode is missing, then the MTX code is recoded to the 'Not in list' code (code=XXXXXXA) of the MATRIX Catalogue in SSD1;
- If the value of the attribute matrixCode contains a dash '-' (i.e. for food items to which correspond sub-codes in the EU coding system as laid down in Part B of the Table in annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005), then the mapping searches in the MATRIX catalogue of SSD1 whether the full code (with 'A' as suffix) is present or not. If it is present, the mapping uses the full MATRIX code; if not, it keeps only the first part of the code and assigns an 'A' in order to get the full MATRIX code. This step is different in case the facet code F20 'part consumed/analysed' A0F4V ('excluding visible fat') is reported for samples of mammals and bird's meat muscle; in this case, the mapping procedure looks first in the MATRIX catalogue to the codes containing the suffix 'B'.
- If the value of the attribute matrixCode does not contain a dash '-', then the mapping assigns the suffix 'A' to it in order to get the full corresponding MATRIX code.

3.3.3.2. prodTreat of SSD1

The FoodEx2 facet F28 ('Process') is mapped to the *prodTreat* SSD1 data element (PRODTR catalogue). The selection of the 'Process' facet code of the MTX catalogue to be used to map to the SSD1 PRODTR codes is carried out following the below steps:

- If no 'Process' facet F28 is present in the MTX term (implicitly or explicitly), then the mapping is directly done to the 'Unprocessed' code (code=T999A in the PRODTR catalogue of SSD1);
- Exception: for the MTX codes related to any type of 'Baby food' the mapping follows a different recoding. The procedure will ensure that process cannot be 'Unprocessed', but if a specific process facet is reported, then the specific value is taken for the mapping. Thus, the recoding to SSD1 is always done to one specific or generic 'Processed' treatment code;
- Exception: the 'Process' facet codes A07JF=Brushing, A07KQ=Freezing and A07KP=Chilling will be ignored in cases where the MTX term implicitly or explicitly contain one or more of the above three facet codes; thus, the EFSA procedure will consider them equivalent to 'Unprocessed'.
- Exception: the two explicit 'Process' facet codes, which are associated to industrial treatments typical for animal milk samples A07HY ('UHT') and A07HZ ('Static sterilisation (in batch or package)'), are mapped in the Catalogue Browser to the SSD1 *prodTreat*=T150A=Milk pasteurisation; these two codes are reportable only for milk samples of animal origin (Business Rule) and will be also considered as 'Unprocessed'. Please note that other children codes under the parent Process code A07HR='Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)' are considered as 'Processed' treatment;
- Considering that the F28 'Process' facet codes are repeatable within a valid MTX term code and that the SSD1 *prodTreat* data element is single value (not repeatable), the mapping makes use of a 'priority list' selecting the most relevant 'Process' facet code in case multiple codes are reported. The implicit facet in a base-term – if present - will always have the highest priority on the explicit facets in identifying the 'Process' code to be mapped to the SSD1 *prodTreat* code.

After the above first steps (i.e. the identification of the reference F28 'Process' code), the mapping process gets the code of the SSD1 PRODTR catalogue:

- The procedure searches in the mapping created by EFSA (i.e. the mapping proposed as 'Production Treatment' implicit attribute readable directly in the Catalogue Browser) for the 'Process' facet MTX code of reference and map it to the corresponding code in the PRODTR catalogue of SSD1.

3.3.3.3. prodProdMethod of SSD1

The FoodEx2 facet F21 ('Production-method') is mapped to the *prodProdMethod* element in SSD1 (this information is useful to flag the organically-produced food samples). For the selection of the reference 'Production-method' facet code these steps are taken:

- Since the SSD2 'Production-method' facet is repeatable and the SSD1 data element *prodProdMethod* is single value (not repeatable), the mapping makes use of a 'priority list' selecting the most relevant 'Production-method' facet code. The implicit facet in a MTX base-term – if present - will always have the highest priority on the explicit facet in identifying the 'Production-method' facet code to be mapped to the *prodProdMethod* code;
- If no 'Production-method' facet is implicitly nor explicitly present in the MTX code reported, then it is recoded to the 'non-organic production' SSD1 code (code=PD09A of the PRODM catalogue in SSD1).

After the above steps (i.e. the identification of the F21 'Production-method' code of reference for the mapping), the process maps the 'Production-method' code to one of the codes in the SSD1 PRODM catalogue:

- The procedure searches in the mapping created by EFSA the 'Production-method' reference MTX facet code and maps it to the corresponding code in the PRODM catalogue of SSD1; thus, the mapping is proposed as indicated in the MTX catalogue under a specific attribute ('Production Method'), implicit attribute readable directly in the Catalogue Browser.

3.3.3.4. prodPack of SSD1

The FoodEx2 facet F19 ('Packaging-material') is mapped to the *prodPack* data element in SSD1. For the selection of the facet 'Packaging-material' code to be used in the recoding the following steps are taken:

- Since the SSD2 'Packaging-material' facet is repeatable and the SSD1 data element *prodPack* is single value (not repeatable), the mapping makes use of a 'priority list' selecting the most relevant 'Production-method' facet code. The implicit facet in a FoodEx2 base-term – if present - will always have the highest priority on the explicit facet in identifying the 'Packaging-material' facet code to be mapped to the *prodPack* code;
- If no 'Packaging-material' facet is neither implicitly nor explicitly present in the FoodEx2 code reported, then it is recoded to a missing value.

After the above steps, the mapping process gets the code of the SSD1 PRODPAC catalogue:

- The procedure searches in the mapping table created by EFSA the facet code 'Packaging-material' reported in SSD2 and maps it to the corresponding code in the PRODPAC catalogue of SSD1. Thus, the mapping is proposed as indicated in the MTX facet catalogue under a specific attribute ('Production Packaging') implicit attribute readable directly in the Catalogue Browser.

3.4. Business rules related to food coding

The Business Rules (BR) set for SSD2 data reporting of the 2018 pesticide monitoring data is the same applied to the SSD1 data collection, once translated to comply with the SSD2 data model. The list of SSD2 BR is provided in a separate document. It should be highlighted that new BR are applicable to both the SSD1 and SSD2 2018 data collection.

In addition to the above rules, specific FoodEx2 BR are applicable, which are needed for the SSD2 data validation against the MatrixTool and the pesticide residue MRL database (see paragraph 3.3.3.).

4. SSD2 data elements for the pesticide monitoring data

In the following paragraphs, directions are provided on the coding specific to the pesticide residue data collection and regarding the compulsory SSD2 data elements. The mandatory data elements are listed in Table 2.

4.1. Programme legal reference progLegalRef (B.02)

The SSD2 coding does not foresee changes compared to the SSD1 coding; this data element is used to specify the legal framework under which the sample was taken and thus defines which MRLs and residue definitions are applicable to the sample. Thus, for the pesticide area the codes of the programme legal reference shall be reported on a mandatory basis by selecting the codes provided in Table 3.

Table 3 Codes to be used to describe the programme legal reference (LEGREF catalogue)

Code value	Code description	Note
N027A	Sample taken under Regulation (EC) No 396/2005	Code to be used for samples of food products defined in Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 (processed and unprocessed products) taken in the framework of the EU-coordinated programme and the national control programmes defined in Article 29 and 30 of this regulation. Samples taken in the framework of Regulation (EC) No 669/2009 should also be coded with N027A.
N028A	Samples of food products falling under Reg. (EU) No 609/2013 and for which MRLs are established in Directives 2006/125/EC and 2006/141/EC	Directives establishing MRL specific to food for infants and young children. Certain products marketed as food for infants and young children do not fall under the baby food legislation and should be reported under N027A (e.g. juices).
N247A	Samples taken under Directive 96/23/EC ¹⁵	Legislative framework for the control of veterinary drug residues in samples of animal origin.
N018A	Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 ¹⁶	Samples not falling under any of the three types of legislation mentioned above (e.g. for reporting results concerning residues of safeners and synergists).

4.2. Sampling strategy – sampStrategy (B.03)

The data element sampling strategy is a mandatory element for pesticide residue monitoring also for the SSD2 data coding and reporting; compared to SSD1 the name of this data element has changed its name, but not the meaning and use. The only valid options for coding must be selected from the catalogue SAMPSTR (Table 4) and are not different from the code selection compared to SSD1.

Table 4 Codes to be used to describe sampling strategy (SAMPSTR catalogue)

Code value	Code description	Note
ST10A	Objective sampling	For samples that were taken as a surveillance sample (random sampling). For example, for the EU-coordinated monitoring programmes samples but also for samples taken under national control programmes, where samples were selected without specific targeting towards products or producers that were likely to be non-compliant.

¹⁵ Council Directive 96/23/EC of 29 April 1996 on measures to monitor certain substances and residues thereof in live animals and animal products and repealing Directives 85/358/EEC and 86/469/EEC and Decisions 89/189/EEC and 91/664/EEC. OJ L 125, 23.5.96, p. 10-32.

¹⁶ Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on official controls performed to ensure the verification of compliance with feed and food law, animal health and animal welfare rules. OJ L 165, 30.4.2004, p. 1-141.

Code value	Code description	Note
ST20A	Selective sampling	For samples taken under the national control programmes which are targeted towards products from a country where higher MRL non-compliance rate was identified in the past for certain food products. Thus, the code is appropriate for samples taken with the aim of detecting non-compliances with legislation, e.g. illegal uses or breaches of legal limits.
ST30A	Suspect sampling	For samples that aimed to enforce provisions of Regulation (EC) No 669/2009 on the increased level of official controls on imported food/feed, for samples taken after RASFF notifications and when the sample is taken from the same consignment that previously was identified as non-compliant or follow-up enforcement samples. The code ST30A should be specifically selected when the sampling is targeted towards a given producer, when there is suspicion or clear evidence that a sample is not compliant with the legislation.

Example 1: How to report a suspect sample, notified under RASFF?

Data element	Code value (catalogue)	Code description	Note
sampMatCode	A0DHD (MTX of FoodEx2)	Basil (holy, sweet)	Please refer to the catalogue for more details on this MTX code.
sampStrategy	ST30A (SAMPSTR)	Suspect sampling	A sample of fresh holy basil checked for the presence of a pesticide residue in the framework of an import control (Regulation (EC) No 669/2009) and because of a RASFF notification.

4.3. progType – Programme type (B.04)

This data element is mandatory, and both its meaning and use have not changed compared to the SSD1 coding; it is used to differentiate samples taken in the framework of the EU coordinated programme as defined in Article 29 of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 from other sampling programmes. For coding, the catalogue SRCTYP must be used considering the conventions described in Table 5.

Table 5 Codes to be used to describe the type of sampling programme (SRCTYP catalogues)

Code value	Code description	Note
K005A	Official (National) programme	For coding of samples taken under national control programmes as defined in Article 30 of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005.
K009A	Official (EU) programme	Samples taken in the framework of the EU coordinated programme (EUCP) as defined in Article 29 of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005. For 2018, the EUCP was defined in Regulation (EU) No 2017/660 ¹⁷ . See also Appendix A –. If the samples were analysed for more pesticides than described in the monitoring regulation, the samples should be coded with K018A (see below).

¹⁷ Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/660 of 6 April 2017 concerning a coordinated multiannual control programme of the Union for 2018, 2019 and 2020 to ensure compliance with maximum residue levels of pesticides and to assess the consumer exposure to pesticide residues in and on food of plant and animal origin. OJ L 94, 7.4.2017, 12-24

Code value	Code description	Note
K018A	Official (National and EU) programme	This code should be used for samples taken in the framework of Regulation (EU) No 201/660 (EU-coordinated control programme) which were analysed for a wider range of pesticides than requested in the EUCP or for other analytes, such as safeners, synergists, residues of veterinary medicinal products (dual use substances).
K019A	Pesticide EU increased control programme on imported food	This code is used to describe samples that were taken under Regulation (EC) No 669/2009 on reinforced border controls. See also Appendix B –.

In Table 6, the only valid combinations of codes for the following data elements are reported. Please see also Table 4, Table 5 and Table 60.

Table 6 Combinations of codes to be used to describe the type of sampling programmes/programme legal reference/sampling strategy (SRCTYP/LEGREF/SAMPSTR catalogues)

		Programme legal reference					
		N027A (Regulation 396/2005)			N028A (Directives 125/2006/EC and 141/2006/EC)	N247A (Directive 96/23/EC)	N018A (Regulation 882/2004)
		EU-coordinated programme	National programmes	Increased import food control	Baby food	Veterinary medicines	e.g. synergists and safeners
Type of sampling programme	K005A (national programmes)	-	ST10A ST20A ST30A	-	ST10A ST20A ST30A	ST10A ST20A ST30A	ST10A ST20A ST30A
	K009A (EU-coordinated programme)	ST10A ST20A	-	-	ST10A ST20A	-	-
	K018A (EU and national programmes)	ST10A ST20A	ST10A ST20A	-	ST10A ST20A	ST10A ST20A	ST10A ST20A
	K019A (increased control Reg 669/2009)	-	-	ST30A	-	-	-

4.4. sampMethod - Sampling method (B.05)

The data element sampling method is mandatory and shall be used as formerly done for the SSD1 coding. Thus, no changes in both its meaning and code selection are brought in the SSD2 version. The catalogue SAMPMD provides the valid codes for this field. Official sampling methods are defined for different food or feed domains. For samples reported to EFSA under the pesticide data collection, the cases summarised in Table 7 are relevant.

Table 7 Codes to be used to describe the type of sampling method (SAMPMD catalogue)

Code value	Code description	Note
N009A	According to Directive 2002/63/EC ^(a)	For samples taken in the framework of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005.
N014A	According to Regulation (EC) No 152/2009 ^(b)	For the official control of feed.

Code value	Code description	Note
N010A	According to Commission Decisions 97/747/EC ^(c) and 98/179/EC ^(d)	For monitoring of certain substances and residues thereof in certain animal products in the framework of Directive 96/23/EC ^(e) .
N001A	Individual/single	To be used for products not covered by the above-mentioned sampling methodologies (e.g. for honey) or for single samples (e.g. one animal or one fruit), which are not representative for a lot/batch.
N008A	Unknown	This code should be used if no information on the sampling method is available.

(a): Commission Directive 2002/63/EC of 11 July 2002 establishing Community methods of sampling for the official control of pesticide residues in and on products of plant and animal origin and repealing Directive 79/700/EEC. OJ L 187/30, 16.7.2002, p. 1–14.

(b): Commission Regulation (EC) No 152/2009 of 27 January 2009 laying down the methods of sampling and analysis for the official control of feed, OJ L54, p 1–130.

(c): Commission Decision of 27 October 1997 fixing the levels and frequencies of sampling provided for by Council Directive 96/23/EC for the monitoring of certain substances and residues thereof in certain animal products (97/747/EC). OJ L 303, 6.11.1997, p. 12–15

(d): Commission Decision of 23 February 1998 laying down detailed rules on official sampling for the monitoring of certain substances and residues thereof in live animals and animal products (98/179/EC). OJ L 65, p 31–98.

(e): Council Directive 96/23/EC of 29 April 1996 on measures to monitor certain substances and residues thereof in live animals and animal products and repealing Directives 85/358/EEC and 86/469/EEC and Decisions 89/187/EEC and 91/664/EEC OJ L 125, 23.5.1996, p. 10–32

4.5. sampPoint - Sampling point (B.07)

This element is mandatory and defines the point in the food chain where the sample was taken. The relevant catalogue is SMPNT and no changes in the selection of the codes occurred from SSD1 to SSD2.

The controlled terminology to be used in the data element is based on a list of terminology developed by EUROSTAT. The list details the activities of establishments at different points in the food chain. The list of activities of the sampling points proposed is subdivided into three hierarchy levels, the first of which is intended to identify the main steps in the production/consumption of food (see Table 80).

Table 8 Groups of codes to be used to describe the type of sampling point from the SMPNT catalogue

Code groups	Code group description	Note
Codes starting with E1	Primary production	Primary production includes both growing crops, rearing of animals and fishery activities.
Codes starting with E3	Manufacturing	
Codes starting with E5	Distribution: wholesale and retail sale	
Codes starting with E6	Packaging	

4.6. sampId - Sample taken identification code (D.01)

This data element is mandatory also when coding in SSD2 format. This data element corresponds to the former SSD1 data element named *labSampCode*; despite the change in the name of the element, its meaning and coding remain unchanged in SSD2. The laboratory sample must be identified by a unique sample identification number not longer than 20 characters. Where multiple analytical results are reported for a sample (e.g. results for different pesticide residues analysed in the same sample using multiresidue methods and/or several single residue methods), the same laboratory sample identification code must be used systematically for the different analytical records/results in the same sample.

4.7. sampCountry - Country of sampling (D.03)

The country of sampling is the country where in accordance with Article 27 of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 the official sample was taken. For coding, the catalogue COUNTRY must be used. Thus, for this data element no changes have been introduced by moving from SSD1 to SSD2.

However, starting from the 2018 pesticide monitoring data collection in 2019, only the codes for the reporting countries (28 EU Member States, Iceland and Norway) are accepted as valid (a new BR has been set-up for this check). Further, another new BR has been set-up to ensure that *sampCountry* matches with the country of the reporting organisation. As a result of this, the country codes for the French Overseas Territories (FOT) are not valid for this data element and in the case the samples were taken by FOT, these must be reported as sampled in France.

4.8. sampY, sampM and sampD - Year, month and day of sampling (D.06, D.08 and D.09)

These mandatory data elements have not changed in SSD2 compared to SSD1. The information on the date of sampling is important to verify the plausibility of the reported assessment of the positive analytical results (the assessment of the 'sample compliance' reported to EFSA) against e.g. the corresponding pesticide MRL applicable for unprocessed (fresh/frozen) primary commodities food samples. The date of analysis should be reported as integers (1, 2 or 4 digits, as appropriate) (e.g. 2018 for the *sampY*, 3 for *sampM*, 19 for *sampD*).

4.9. sampMatType - Type of matrix (E.01)

This data element is not mandatory for the pesticide monitoring data collection; it is a new data element, which did not exist in SSD1. It defines the type of matrix (food or feed) that is analysed. The codes for this element are listed in the MTXTYP catalogue (see Table 9); in the frame of the pesticide residues data collection the two relevant and recommended code to be selected are: S019A (Food sample) or S026A (Feed sample). Please note that the code 'Animal sample' shall not be reported in the frame of the pesticide monitoring data collection. Food samples of animal origin intended for consumers must be always reported with the code 'Food'.

Table 9 Codes from the catalogue MTXTYP for reporting the *sampMatType*

Code value	Code description	Note
S000A	Animal sample	Not advised to be selected; to report food samples of animal origin, please use the code S019A
S019A	Food sample	Code relevant for the pesticide residues monitoring
S023A	Food simulant	Not to be selected
S026A	Feed sample	Code relevant for the pesticide residues monitoring; this code should only be selected in case the feed item tested is referring to feed exclusively used for animal consumption
S027A	Environmental sample	Not advised to be selected
S030A	Unknown	Not advised to be selected
S031A	Contact material	Not advised to be selected

4.10. SampMatCode - Coded description of the matrix of the sample taken (E.02)

This data element represents the major difference introduced in the SSD when moving from SSD1 to SSD2. It is a mandatory data element and needs to be used to describe the sample taken and analysed, by using the most appropriate FoodEx2 code, which is selectable from the MTX catalogue. As indicated above (see section 3.3 on FoodEx2) this field allows the reporting of a compound code.

The structure of the code is made up of a term taken from the applicable data collection domain (base term), selected by the data collection domain linked to the data collection.

This 'base term' can then be followed by the combination of facet descriptors, which can be either pre-assigned in the FoodEx2 system (implicit facets) or defined by the data provider (explicit facets)¹⁸.

The data provider will always have to describe the matrix with the most detailed level of information available using FoodEx2; additional information (e.g. the full textual sample description) can also be reported in the E.03 field *sampMatText* (free text data element)¹⁹.

This will provide a double check for the codes reported in case of data quality problems. Finally, an additional comment field is also available to provide additional information regarding the matrix (E.10 *sampMatInfo* element of the system).

In the section below, some examples are provided in regards the selection of the appropriate code for the data element *sampMatCode*.

Example 2: How to code a sample of organic, unprocessed carrots?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A00QH	Carrots	For the implicit attributes of this code from the FoodEx2 browser, the MTX code is mapped to MATRIX (SSD1) code P0213020-000. This code refers to a Raw Primary Commodity (RPC) ¹⁸ and the facets F01 (Source Facet) = 'carrot (as plant)'. The F28 facet ('Process' Facet) is not implicitly encoded in the MTX code. Thus, this code refers to a raw/unprocessed carrots sample. In addition, in the browser, the facet 21 ('Production-method') is not preassigned. Thus, to report an organic sample of carrots this facet must be explicitly reported by the data provider.
A07SE	Organic production	To add this attribute to the base term for the RPC=Carrots (A00QH), choose in the Catalogue Browser the Facets list and select the 'Production-method' list of codes. Thus, select the attribute 'Organic production' (A07SE). For the pesticide residue data collection, the following 'Production-method' facet codes are suggested, but other codes are also allowed: A07SE (Organic production), A0C6Y (Conventional non-intensive production) for non-organic production and A17LS (Integrated pest management (IPM)). Other relevant codes could be: A07RV ('Farmed/cultivated/aquaculture') and A07RY ('Wild or gathered or hunted'). If no production method code is provided, EFSA will assume by default that sample tested was 'non-organic production'. Therefore, to report any organic sample the 'Organic production' (A07SE) F21 code shall always be explicitly added to the base term describing the food tested.

¹⁸ The description of the 'base-term' concept and the principal types of food groups in FoodEx2 (e.g. the Raw Primary Commodities' (RPC) and RPC derivatives/ingredients are described in the EFSA publication 'The food classification and description system FoodEx2', document available also at: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/sp.efsa.2015.EN-804/epdf>

¹⁹ In its capacity as a European Union agency, documents held by EFSA (i.e. documents which it has produced or received from third parties, including Member States, all areas of its activity) are subject to Regulation (EC) No 1049/2001 on public access to documents ('PAD Regulation') and to Regulation (EC) No 1367/2006 on public access to environmental information as per the interpretation of the European Union Courts (Regulation (EC) No 1367/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council). When submitting data to EFSA, Member States should be aware of the stringent transparency obligations by which EFSA is bound, in application of the legal framework and the relevant case law interpreting the specific provisions concerned. This is particularly relevant if the data contain commercially sensitive information and/or personal data as defined in Article 3(1) of Regulation (EU) 2018/17259. Before transmitting data to EFSA, Member States should take into consideration the complex nature of the application of the relevant exceptions to disclosure and might consider facilitating this process by including only information which they consider may be made publicly accessible via access to documents' release.

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A0C0S	Unprocessed	In order to specify Unprocessed samples the food item should be first selected in the catalogue browser and then "described" by means of the Process facet (F28). Browsing the "Process" list of codes the 'Unprocessed' (A0C0S) can be retrieved in the group of 'Generic process descriptors' (A0C0Q). Please note that if the processing facet is not specified, EFSA will automatically consider that the sample tested is 'Unprocessed'.
Complete code	A00QH#F21.A07SE\$F28.A0C0S	Please note that the order of the facets codes to be reported in the final code is not bound; thus, in this example, the code A00QH#F28.A0C0S\$F21.A07SE and the code A00QH#F21.A07SE\$F28.A0C0S are equivalent.

Example 3: How to report the results for a pesticide residue in an unprocessed sample of clementine?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A01CE	Clementine	<p>The pesticide MRL applicable to clementine samples are the ones set for mandarins. Therefore, in the MTX code implicit attributes window, the MTX clementine code A01CE is reported under the parent MTX code A01CB set for the group of 'Mandarins and similar'.</p> <p>In order to select the correct MTX code the data provider is recommended to use the 'search' function in the Catalogue Browser. In the search window it is suggested to search also for the matrixCode attribute; in this case the code to be searched for is the matrixCode attribute=P0110050-002 (corresponding to the EC food sub-code 0110050-002 as indicated in Part B of Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005), which corresponds to clementine. By searching for 'P0110050-002' the Catalogue Browser will directly indicate the code A01CE.</p> <p>Alternatively, the data provider can also search for the scientific name of the food as indicated in Annex I of Regulation 396/2005 (in this case the scientific name is <i>Citrus Clementina</i> or <i>Citrus reticulata Blanco</i>).</p> <p>According to the MTX, the base-term code A01CE does not contain an implicit facet for the 'Process'; thus, this code can be used to code unprocessed clementine samples.</p>

In SSD1 the 'processed' food samples were coded by selecting an appropriate processing code from the ones available in the catalogue PRODTR. In FoodEx2 (SSD2), all processed food items are already present in the MTX catalogues with the implicit facet F28 'Process' descriptor (code) already pre-assigned. In principle, the data provider will only have to identify via the FoodEx2 catalogue browser the most appropriate code/food description for the tested food sample. The above is not applicable for specific cases (exceptions) that will be described later in the paragraph. Here below is reported an example on how to code a processed sample.

Example 4: How to code a sample of orange juice?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A03AM	Juice, orange	<p>In order to select the appropriate MTX code for a transformed, processed food sample, it is recommended to browse the catalogue using the 'Search' function (it is recommended to use the 'Exact Match' option for this function) and by typing the name of the tested food ('orange juice', in this case). Please do not start searching for the base-term 'oranges' and then add the facet F28 Process 'Juicing'.</p> <p>In the Implicit attributes window of the FoodEx2 Catalogue Browser you will not find this code mapped to any matrixCode attribute; this will be the case also for all other MTX codes associated to food considered as RPC <i>Derivatives</i>. Thus, is correct because the MATRIX catalogue only contains code associated to raw, unprocessed food items.</p> <p>In the Implicit Facets list associated to this MTX code you can see that this base-term code is already made-up of the F27 Source-commodities code=A0DZB=Oranges and F28 Process code=A07LN=Juicing.</p>

Example 5: How to code a sample of orange juice, from concentrate?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A03CA	Juice concentrate, orange	<p>As in the previous example (Example 4) in order to choose the appropriate MTX code for a transformed, processed food sample, it is recommended to browse the catalogue, use the Search function and type the name of the tested food (e.g. 'orange concentrate' or 'orange juice', in this case) and then select the most appropriate term returned by the textual search. Please do not start searching for the base-term 'oranges' and then add the facet F28 Process 'Juicing'.</p> <p>In the Implicit attributes window of the FoodEx2 Catalogue Browser you will not find this code mapped to any of the MATRIX code catalogue (no matrixCode attribute is displayed); thus, this is because the MATRIX catalogue only contained code associated to raw, unprocessed food items.</p> <p>In the Implicit facets window in the Browser associated to this term, you can see that this base-term code is already made-up of the F27 Source-commodities code A0DZB (Oranges); in addition, two implicit facets are already included in this base-term: F28 Process facet code A07LN (Juicing) and F28 Process facet code A07KF (Concentration/evaporation).</p>

Example 6: How to code a sample of a processed sample not listed in the 'Reporting' Hierarchy of FoodEx2 (e.g. banana juice)?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A0BYA	Fruit juices (100% from named source)	MTX codes for some processed food are not available in the Catalogue Browser. This is the case for 'Banana Juice' and the MTX code in this case must be built by the data provider using the appropriate facet code. To start with, the data provider will need to select the 'Fruit juices (100% from named source)' MTX code (code A0BYA) and then add the F27 Source-commodity explicit attribute 'Common banana' (code A01LC). Please do not start searching for the base-term 'Common banana' and then add the facet F28 Process 'Juicing'. This MTX code will need to be added to the Facet F27 'Source-commodity'.
A01LC	Common banana	
Complete code	A0BYA#F27.A01LC	

As mentioned earlier in the paragraph, there are a few exceptions on the way of the explicit or implicit facet coding and mapping of certain groups of 'processed' (or apparently 'processed') food samples.

In the next examples, details on the topic are provided to guide the data providers.

Dried food products belonging to the pesticide residues MRL food group of 'Pulses' (EC food group 0300000 according to Annex I of Regulation 396/2005 and MATRIX food group P0300000A) and to one of its sub-groups should be always considered as 'unprocessed'. Therefore, the explicit facet F28 ('Process' facet) equal to 'Drying (dehydration)'=A07KG should not be added to the base-term selected. The base-terms in FoodEx2 for all food of the group 'pulses' (A012R codes) implicitly contains the pre-assigned 'Drying (dehydration)'=A07KG; however, be aware that specific mapping rules apply to this food group items as described in section 3.3.3.2. According to these mapping rules, which are specific to the pesticide monitoring data collection, once the data will be transmitted to EFSA in SSD2, they will be remapped to 'unprocessed' samples for data validation and analysis purposes.

Example 7: How to report results for dry peas (pulses), for example for garden peas (i.e. ('mangetout' peas)?

FoodEx2 MTX code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A0DCD	Peas (dry) and similar	Peas (dry seeds) are classified in the MRL food group of 'pulses'. The MATRIX code used in SSD1 was P0300030A, which corresponds to the FoodEx2 code A0DCD ('Peas (dry) and similar'), under the 'Pulses (dried legume seeds)' food group (MTX group code A012R). Should you wish to report a specific variety of dry peas (e.g. garden peas/'Mangetout'), you can select in the 'Reporting' hierarchy for 'Peas (dry) and similar' the more specific FoodEx2 child codes (e.g. A013J for the garden peas).

FoodEx2 MTX code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
		Drying of pulses to reach standard moisture content (ca. 15 – 19 %) is not considered as processing. If the sample analysed complies with the description of Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005, the product is considered as being 'Unprocessed' even if it appears to be dried. In this case, the FoodEx2 F28 'Process' facet code for 'Dehydration' shall not be reported as it will not be appropriate in this case. Please note that for samples of pulses, even though the implicit attribute 'process' is encoded in the FoodEx2 term, the Food code procedures foresees the mapping of the pulses samples to unprocessed samples in the frame of the pesticide monitoring data collection and analysis (see section 3.3.3.2).
		Please also note that the FoodEx2 code associated to the base-terms A00PX ('Peas with pods') and A012G ('Peas (without pods) and similar') refer to the fresh peas with or without pods, to which corresponds the MATRIX code P0260040A. Therefore, the FoodEx2 code A00PX (nor all its children MTX codes) should not be selected in this case, as it applies to fresh peas varieties.

Example 8: How to report results for fresh green peas (without pods)?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A012J	Garden peas	Fresh peas without pods are not classified in the MRL group of 'pulses' (see Example 7). They are classified in the MRL food group of 'Legume vegetables' 0260000 and the sample is made up of the whole product (only fresh pea seeds). In this example, the code associated to one of the many children codes have been selected from the parent group 'Peas (without pods) and similar' (A012G). Please note that in the Catalogue Browser this term is associated to the matrixCode attribute P02060040-001 (SSD1 MATRIX code=P02060040).
		The term A012J is not including an implicit process attribute 'Process' (facet F28) on the sample. Thus, by selecting this code, it means that you have tested and are reporting to EFSA a sample of unprocessed food item. According to the EFSA mapping steps (please see section 3.3.3.2) if the Facet F28 code A0C0S 'Unprocessed' is not specifically reported, EFSA will automatically consider this sample as 'unprocessed'.

The MRL for pesticide residues are set separately for samples of meat 'muscle' (sample of meat analysed after discarding the visible fat part) and for 'fat' from meat; this difference was addressed in the MATRIX catalogue (SSD1) by allocating two distinct codes (e.g. for bovine meat, the codes P1012010B 'Muscle bovine' and P1012020A 'muscle fat' were available for selection); in particular, all the 'muscle' codes related to all different farm animal species contained the letter 'B' as code suffix. In SSD2 this distinction is not directly captured by the FoodEx2 classification; thus, for reporting the 'muscle' samples tested for pesticide residue MRL compliance, the most appropriate FoodEx2 codes from the food group 'Mammals and birds meat (under the group code **AOEYH**)' shall be selected. In addition, in order to report sample of muscle without fat, the specific facet code 'Excluding visible fat' should be always explicitly added from 'part consumed/analysed' F20 facet catalogue. An example is reported below.

Example 9: How to report results for mammals and bird's meat 'muscle' (e.g. bovine muscle)?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A01QX	Cow, ox or bull fresh meat	In this example, the coding is proposed for a sample of bovine muscle analysed after discarding the visible fat. Differently, if the sample tested is not muscle, another specific term should be selected.
A0F4V	Excluding visible fat	In case of any type of farmed mammals and bird 'muscle' sample (i.e. meat samples without visible/trimmable fat) is analysed, its results shall <u>always</u> be reported with the F20 'part consumed/analysed' facet code A0F4V ('Excluding visible fat'). Please be aware that if this facet is not included in the complete FoodEx2 code, the sample will not be mapped to meat 'muscle'.
Complete code	A01QX#F20.A0F4V	These SSD2 code combined match to the MATRIX code P1012010B in SSD1.

Example 10: How to report results for wild vertebrate animal e.g. deer fresh meat from hunted, not farmed animals?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A01SA	Deer fresh meat	<p>Under Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 a food group MRL is set to 'Wild terrestrial vertebrate animals', which is coded by EC as 1070000. This group covers feather wild game, furred wild game and kangaroos. However, <i>wild</i> game can be considered as either hunted or farmed; the same applies to kangaroos.</p> <p>In order to distinguish hunted animals that grew in <i>wild</i> conditions and then gathered from <i>wild</i> animals raised in the farm, EFSA recommends to follow the directions given in this example to report wild hunted animal food samples.</p> <p>In this example, the coding is proposed for a sample of fresh deer meat from a hunted animal.</p> <p>If the sample tested concerned only the 'muscle' (without visible/trimmable fat), the data provider should always also specify it by using the facet F20 as indicated in the previous example ('Part consumed/analysed' facet code A0F4V = 'Excluding visible fat'). See Example 9.</p>
A07RY	Wild or gathered or hunted	<p>In case of any type of wild terrestrial vertebrate animals that was hunted/gathered into the wild, the F21 facet 'Production-method' code A07RY 'Wild or gathered or hunted' should always be reported.</p> <p>Please be aware that if this facet is not included in the complete FoodEx2 code, the sample will not be considered/mapped to the wild animal food group code P1070000 of the MATRIX catalogue and in EC food classification.</p> <p>Please note also that in case the tested sample was from a wild animal (deer) that was farmed, the facet 'Production-method' code A07RY 'Wild or gathered or hunted' should not be reported.</p>

Complete code	A01SA#F21.A07RY
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Dried food products belonging to the pesticide residues MRL food group of 'Herbal infusions' (EC food group 0630000 according to Annex I of Regulation 396/2005) and to one of its sub-groups should be always considered unprocessed, i.e. the explicit facet F28 ('Process' facet) equal to 'Drying (dehydration)'=A07KG should not be added to the base-term selected. Specific mapping rules apply to the Herbal infusion food items as described in section 3.3.3.2.

Example 11: How to report results for dry chamomile flowers (herbal infusion)?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A03JC	Chamomile	Herbal infusions, according to Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005, are dried products. Chamomile samples should be coded with one of the FoodEx2 code of the group A0D9E (Chamomile and similar) under the main group A03JB (Flowers used for herbal infusions). In the FoodEx2 Catalogue Browser you will notice that the term of this example (A03JC) is mapped to the MATRIX code P0631010 (<i>matrixCode</i> attribute=P0631010-000) and that no implicit 'Process' facet is included in the code.
		If the sample analysed complies with the description of Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005, the product is considered as being unprocessed when it is in a dried form. Thus, in case of a sample of dried leaves of chamomile for herbal infusion, the tested sample is unprocessed. If the data provider add a facet to the base term A03JC, the EFSA recoding procedure to SSD1 will map it to unprocessed food sample (please see also 3.3.3.2).

Food products that were subject to mechanical crushing operation without segregation or removal of parts of the crop (e.g. chopping, grinding) should be also reported as 'unprocessed', i.e. the explicit facet F28 ('Process' facet) codes corresponding to 'Drying (dehydration)'=A07KG should never be added to the base-term selected. Typically, this is the case of spices samples. An example is reported below.

Example 12: How to report results for ground/milled spices, e.g. nutmeg?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A018J	Nutmeg seed	This FoodEx2 term corresponds to the P0810090A (MATRIX catalogue in SSD1) and is described in the Catalogue Browser with the attribute <i>matrixCode</i> =P0810090-000. The term 'Nutmeg seed' (A018J) does not contain an implicit 'Process' facet descriptor 'Drying (dehydration)' (code A07KG).
		Samples that have been ground, crushed, milled, powdered and/or pulverised are to be considered as 'unprocessed' samples, if the process does not involve a separation of a certain fraction (like milling of cereals). Thus, it is not necessary to explicitly code this sample with the 'Drying (dehydration)'=A07KG F28 facet code. Typically, this applies to dry spices marketed e.g. in glasses.

Example 13: How to report results for a sample of pasteurised/sterilized milk of animal origin (cow's milk)

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A02LV	Cow milk	Milk from animals (not milk of plant origin) are found in the Catalogue Browser in the food group 'Milk' (A02LT); this code is not reportable, please select one of the children code available under A02LT. In case the fat content of the sample is not known/determined, the code Cow milk (A02LV) can be selected. If more details are available on the fat content (e.g. low fat, skimmed milk sample), then one of the sub-codes of the code for cow's milk (A02LV) can be chosen.
A07HZ	Statical sterilisation (in batch or package)	Animal milk samples (cow, goat, sheep, etc.) that have been pasteurised, filtrated, sterilised and/or subjected to other treatments with the purpose to extend their shelf-life have to be reported with the most appropriate F28 'Process' facet among the ones available in the facet group code 'Thermal treatment heating for preservation' (A07HR). In this example, the facet code 'Statical sterilisation (in batch or package)' (A07HZ) has been selected. However, in the summary data analysis presented in the EU Report on Pesticide Residues, the results for milk samples reported with one of the two 'Process' facet codes A07HZ (Statical sterilisation (in batch or package)) and A07HY (UHT) will be mapped and pooled with milk samples reported as 'Unprocessed' (see also 3.3.3.2).
Complete code	A02LV#F28.A07HZ	

Example 14: How to report a sample of a pasteurised food (e.g. pasteurised chicken eggs)?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A031G	Hen eggs	The specific code selected in this example belongs to the code group 'Whole eggs' (A031G) and it does not contain an implicit facet for 'Process'. Thus, by selecting this code and without adding any explicit 'Process' facet code, it is considered that the tested eggs sample was fresh/unprocessed. Please note that, according to Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005, the MRL set for chicken eggs shall be checked against the residue level measured in the whole product after removal of the shell.
A07HV	Pasteurisation	For pasteurised food samples which have a different form than animal milk, the pasteurisation 'Process' codes A07HZ ('Statical sterilisation (in batch or package)') and A07HY ('UHT') shall not be selected. It is recommended to use instead, one of the following codes: A07HT ('Low pasteurisation (thermisation)'), A07HV ('Pasteurisation'), A07HX ('High pasteurisation (extending shelf life)') and A07JA ('Hot-filling'). The latter codes are automatically mapped by EFSA to the previous SSD1 codes 'T151A' on 'Pasteurisation'.
Complete code	A031G#F28.A07HV	

The code to be selected to report 'baby food' samples are indicated in the next table (Table 10).

Table 10 MATRIX (SSD1) and their corresponding MTX (SSD2) codes relevant reporting of results for any type of 'baby food'²⁰

MATRIX code (SSD1)	MATRIX code description (SSD1)	FoodEx2 MTX catalogue term code	FoodEx2 base-term description	Note
PX100003A	Processed cereal-based foods for infants and young children	A03QX or one of its children codes, as appropriate	Processed cereal-based foods for infants and young children	Definition of this code(s) as provided in Regulation (EU) No 609/2013: Processed cereal-based food means (i) food intended to fulfil the particular requirements of infants and young children in good health and intended for use by infants while they are being weaned, and of young children in good health as a supplement to their diet and/or for their progressive adaptation, to ordinary food; and (ii) pertaining to one of the following categories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simple cereals which are or must be reconstituted with milk or other appropriate nutritious liquids, - Cereals with an added high protein food which are or must be reconstituted with water or other protein free liquid, - Pastas which are to be used after cooking in boiling water or other appropriate liquids, - Rusks and biscuits which are to be used either directly or, after pulverisation, with the addition of water, milk or other suitable liquids.

²⁰ The description of MTX code **A03PX** (i.e. 'Food for infants and young children') recalls the description of the former MATRIX code PX100000A. However, the data providers should not select this high hierarchical level code to report their baby food samples (, this code is not mapped to the matrixCode attribute PX100000A). The reason for this is that the MATRIX code PX100000A was introduced and considered as a generic code and it only had to be used if none of the other former four Baby Food related MATRIX codes were appropriate to describe the sample. Thus, the code did not reflect any Baby Food group otherwise described by EC legislation. Considering that the FoodEx2 provides for several base-term codes related to Baby Food that can be used to describe the food tested, the code A03PX shall **not** be selected; instead, a more specific code should be selected, as indicated in the table.

MATRIX code (SSD1)	MATRIX code description (SSD1)	FoodEx2 MTX catalogue term code	FoodEx2 base-term description	Note
PX100004A	Infant formulae	A0EQM or one of its children codes, as appropriate	Infant formulae	Definition of this code as provided in Regulation (EU) No 609/2013: Infant formulae means food intended for use by infants during the first months of life and satisfying by itself the nutritional requirements of such infants until the introduction of appropriate complementary feeding.
PX100005A	Follow-on formulae	A0EQL or one of its children codes, as appropriate	Follow-on formulae	Definition of this code as provided in Regulation (EU) No 609/2013: Follow-on formula means food intended for use by infants when appropriate complementary feeding is introduced, and which constitutes the principal liquid element in a progressively diversified diet of such infants.
PX100001A	Baby foods other than processed cereal-based foods ²¹	A03RC or one of its children codes Or A03RL or one of its children codes	Ready-to-eat meal for infants and young children Or Other food for infants and children	<p>Definition of this MATRIX code as provided in Regulation (EU) No 609/2013²²: Baby food means food intended to fulfil the particular requirements of infants in good health while they are being weaned, and of young children in good health as a supplement to their diet and/or for their progressive adaptation to ordinary food, excluding: (i) processed cereal-based food; and (ii) milk-based drinks and similar products intended for young children.</p> <p>This code should therefore be applied for e.g. ready to eat food marketed in jars, containing fruit, vegetables, meat or fish and other ingredients.</p> <p>Some food products offered for all ages including infants and young children (e.g. herbal teas) national competent authorities have different views on whether these products should be encoded as baby food or based on the classification of Reg. (EC) No 396/2005.</p> <p>If according to the national competent authorities the product is compliant with the definition of baby food in Reg. (EU) No 609/2013, one of the proposed MTX codes should be used for describing the sample (see Example 15) to report results on herbal teas labelled as baby food and Example 16 to report results on herbal teas for the entire population.</p>

²¹ The description of the product category will be aligned with Reg. (EU) No 609/2013. The MatrixTool and catalogue browser will be updated accordingly.

²² Regulation (EU) No 609/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 June 2013 on food intended for infants and young children, food for special medical purposes, and total diet replacement for weight control and repealing Council Directive 92/52/EEC, Commission Directives 96/8/EC, 1999/21/EC, 2006/125/EC and 2006/141/EC, Directive 2009/39/EC of

Example 15: How to report the results for a pesticide residue in herbal tea for infants that according to national authorities fall under Regulation (EC) No 609/2013?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A03RM	Herbal infusions (beverages) specific for infants and young children, liquid	Code to be used if according to the national interpretation of the definition for baby food, the product analysed falls under Regulation (EU) No 609/2013.
or	or	
A16GS	Herbal infusions (beverages) specific for infants and young children, dry	
A0C0R	Processed	Baby food products are processed products. The EFSA mapping procedures specific for the pesticide residues monitoring will anyway automatically consider the baby food samples as processed (see also section 3.3.3.2), despite the implicit or explicit 'Process' facet of the reported code. Thus, for coding the food item in this example it is not necessary to report the 'Process' facet F28. However, if this facet is reported, it will not create an error.
Complete code	A03RM#F28.A0C0R or A16GS#F28.A0C0R	

Example 16: How to report the results for a pesticide residue in herbal tea for infants that according to national authorities does not fall under Regulation (EC) No 609/2013?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A03JC	Chamomile	In this example, a sample of chamomile herbal tea labelled as indicated for babies is considered.
A0C0R	Processed	Code from the Facet catalogue F28 'Process' to be reported.
Complete code	A03JC#F28.A0C0R	

In the context of the pesticide monitoring data collection, also feed samples can be reported; these samples are to be reported only for crops exclusively used for animal feed purposes (e.g. wheat straw). For feed samples, harmonised EU MRLs are not yet established under Regulation (EC) No 396/2005. It should be highlighted that for feed products that were produced from products listed in Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 396/2005, the existing EU MRLs apply, considering the appropriate processing factors.

The 'Reporting' Hierarchy of the Catalogue Browser is made up of three main groups, one of those is the 'Feed' group (A0BB9) (see **Figure 2**). Please note that the textual description of all MTX codes under the 'Feed' group (and their children) always contains the wording '(feed)' (e.g. the code A05CR='Barley grain (feed)'). This explicit wording is considered useful to highlight that two MTX codes apparently referring to the same item (e.g. barley grains) can be reported as food intended for human consumption (e.g. 'Barley grains'=A000P) and as feed only intended for animal feeding purposes (e.g. 'Barley grain (feed)'=A05CR). In the Catalogue Browser, the scope Note for the MTX

the European Parliament and of the Council and Commission Regulations (EC) No 41/2009 and (EC) No 953/2009. OJ L 181, 29.6.2013, p.35-56.

code 'Feed' (A0BB9) indicates that the Feed codes refer to crops or products normally used only as feed and not for human consumption. Those foods that are also used as feed are not included in this group but are instead in the appropriate 'Food' category.

Figure 2: Feed classification/groups of the MTX catalogue of the FoodEX2

Example 17: How to code a sample of feed?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A0BKY	Cereals straw (feed)	This example indicates the most appropriate code for reporting a feed sample of 'wheat straw'.
A0BFJ	Soya (bean) meal (feed)	In this example, the MTX code proposed was selected to report a feed sample of soya meal.

Example 18: What are the only feed samples that were reported in the framework of the 2017 pesticide monitoring data collection in SSD2?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet
A0BDE	Wheat (feed)
A0BFM	Soya beans, extruded (feed)
A0BFT#F28.A0C0R	Sunflower seed meal (feed) – processed
A0BL9#F21.A07SE	Lucerne; [Alfalfa] (feed) - organic production
A0BTK#F28.A0C0R	Laying hens / Complete feed (feed) – processed

Differently from the SSD1, the SSD2 allows, by means of the FoodEx2, to select an existing code for a composite food item (i.e. a sample of food made up of more than one ingredient). By using the FoodEx2 Catalogue Browser it will be easy to identify the most commonly consumed composite food. To select the most appropriate MTX term, please start by browsing the existing catalogue terms in the main (high level) food group 'Composite dishes' (see also Example 19).

Example 19: How to code a sample of frozen pizza ‘Margherita’ made up mainly of wheat flour, tomato sauce and cheese?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A03ZP	Pizza and similar with cheese topping	The group of codes under the MTX code A03ZN (‘Pizza and pizza-like dishes’) allows the data provider to select the most appropriate children code to better describe/code the sample tested. In this example, a FoodEx2 code is proposed to describe a pizza mainly made-up with tomatoes and mozzarella.
		Please note that the code A03ZP already implicitly includes two F04 ‘Ingredient’ facet attributes: Cheese (A02QE) and Pizza base Cooked (A006Q).
		Considering the large varieties of pizza toppings and fillings, more detailed information on the characterising ingredients with facet F04 can be provided with additional facets descriptors than the ones already implicitly included in the selected code.
A07KQ	Freezing	Code from the Facet catalogue F28 ‘Process’
Complete code	A03ZP#F28A07KQ	

Despite that FoodEx2 addresses the coding on a very large variety of items (both simple and composite food), it might be possible that a given food code cannot be found in the ‘Reporting’ FoodEx2 hierarchy (see Example 20 and Example 21).

Example 20: How to report pesticide residues in a sample of mixed fruit and vegetable juice?

FoodEx2 MTX catalogue code	Code description for the base-term/facet	Note
A03DB	Mixed fruit and vegetable juices	This sample is considered as composite food, which is made up of more than one processed ingredients.
		Please note that the code A03DB already implicitly includes two F28 ‘Process’ facet: Mixing (A0CRL) and Juicing (A07LN).
		Considering the varieties of fruit and vegetables that are at the origin of this mixed juice, more detailed information on the characterising ingredients can be provided with additional facets descriptors (facet F04).

Example 21: How to code a sample that is not present in the FoodEx2 'Reporting' hierarchy, but is included in the 'Exposure' hierarchy?²³

Code description selected from FoodEx2 'Exposure' hierarchy	MTX code from the 'Exposure' hierarchy	MTX code description selected from FoodEx2 'Reporting' hierarchy	Proposed FoodEx2 code from the 'Reporting' hierarchy	Note
Breakfast cereals	A00CV	'Mixed breakfast cereals' Or 'Cereal flakes and similar'	A00EL or A04QY	Once one of the two codes from the 'Reporting' hierarchy are selected, additional coded description can be provided by using the attributes (codes) in e.g. 'Ingredients' facet F04.
Spices	A016S	Seed spice, or bud spices or aril spices or bark spices	One of the spice groups' codes under the main group of A0EZM for 'Spices'	A general high-level code for the generic term 'Spices' is not available in the MTX catalogue. It is recommended to select at least a more specific code for one of the sub-groups of spices (e.g. seed spices, bark spices).
Coffee ingredients	A03GJ	Coffee ingredients (RPC derivatives) Coffee imitate ingredients	A0C6A (or one of its children codes) or A03GS (or one of its children codes)	Proposal for coding made on the assumption that the sample tested refers to ingredients for hot beverage preparations from coffee beans (A0C6A) or from other surrogate ingredients (A03GS).
Cocoa ingredients	A03HE	Cocoa powder or Cocoa mass	A03HG or A03HJ	Proposals for coding made on the assumption that the sample tested refers to products whose main ingredient is derived from cocoa beans and it is used for hot beverage preparations.
Other stone fruits (e)	A04SE	Other stone fruits	A01HB	Further description of the sample can be provided using the appropriate facets codes and/or by free text in the SSD2 data element sampMatText (see 4.11) in case it is considered that the textual description of the selected code from the MTX catalogue is not sufficient.

Table 11 MTX (SSD2) and corresponding MATRIX (SSD1) codes to be used to report specific *unprocessed* food items (in particular, but not only, tested under Regulation (EC) No 669/2009 on reinforced import controls) and for which specific MRL are not set in the EU MRL legislation (see also Appendix B –).

SSD2 term (MTX catalogue)	SSD2 code (MTX catalogue)	SSD1 term (MATRIX catalogue)	SSD1 code (MATRIX catalogue)	Note
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²³ The table in this Example provides for the full compilation of FoodEx2 codes used in the framework of the 2017 pesticide monitoring data collection (which was making use of the FoodEx2 'Exposure' hierarchy), which are not present in the 'Reporting' hierarchy (which is the only FoodEx2 hierarchy of reference for the 2018 pesticide monitoring data collection).

SSD2 term (MTX catalogue)	SSD2 code (MTX catalogue)	SSD1 term (MATRIX catalogue)	SSD1 code (MATRIX catalogue)	Note
Pitayas	A0DQS	Pitahaya (dragon fruit)	P0162040-001A	To report pitahaya samples, please do not use the code for 'Prickly pears' (code A01KD), even if the same MRL apply.
Wolfberries (Goji berries)	A0DMR	Goji berries	P0231010-005A	To report fresh goji berries samples, please do not use the code for 'Tomatoes' (code A0DMX), even if the same MRL apply, nor the code MTX A00JH 'Gojiberry' should be selected. The correct code is A0DMR because the correct scientific name (<i>Lycium barabarum L.</i> , as per Part B of Annex I of Regulation 396/2005) corresponds to the FoodEx2 code A0DMR, which is then mapped to the MATRIX (SSD1) sub-code P0231010-005.
Chili peppers	A00JB	Chili peppers	P0231020-001A	To report chili peppers samples, please do not use the code for 'Sweet peppers' (code A00JB), even if the same MRL apply.
Sopropos	A00JY	Bitter melon	P0232030-007A	To report fresh bitter melon samples, please do not use the code for 'Courgettes' (code A00JR), even if the same MRL apply.
Chinese broccoli	A00FQ	Chinese broccoli	P0241010-002A	To report fresh Chinese broccoli samples, please do not use the code for 'Broccoli' (code A00FN).
Coriander leaves	A00XF	Coriander leaves	P0256030-004A	To report coriander leaves samples, please do not use the code for 'Celery leaves' (code A00XA).
Holy basil	A0DHD	Basil (holy, sweet)	P0256080-009A	To report fresh basil (holy, sweet) samples, please do not use the code for 'Basil' (code A00VV), even if the same MRL apply.
Peppermint	A00YB	Mint	P0256080-020A	To report fresh mint samples, please do not use the code for 'Basil' (code A00VV), even if the same MRL apply.
Curry leaves	A00XG	Curry leaves	P0256090-001A	To report curry leaves samples, please do not use the code for 'Laurel' (code A00XG), even if the same MRL apply.
Yardlong beans (with pods)	A00PF	Yardlong beans	P0260010-017A	To report fresh yard-long beans samples, please do not use the code for 'Beans (with pods) and similar' (code A00PC), even if the same MRL apply.

The past *prodCode* 'XXXXXXA' (i.e. food code 'Not in list'), from the SSD1 MATRIX catalogue, referring to general descriptors of the food tested and used to report composite food items, is not present in the FoodEx2 MTX catalogue. The FoodEx2 catalogue should be sufficiently extensive to cover all the

food items to be reported. A suitable detailed term may not be found. The reason for this might be that the food group has not been considered for inclusion or it was deemed of minor relevance.

Nevertheless, if it is considered needed, FoodEx2 allows the reporting of a 'new food', by creating a new code customised by the data provider. A new base-term code should be created and reported only in exceptional cases and only after having verified that the tested food product is not already addressed in the FoodEx2 catalogue. In case a new code is created by the data provider and reported in the data element *sampMatCode*, the additional free text description can be provided in the data element *sampMatText* (SSD2 data element E02, see also Section 4.11). Instructions on how to create a new code are provided (EFSA, 2015) and the reader is recommended to read them.

4.11. sampMatText - Text description of the matrix of the sample taken (E.03)

This free text data element is not mandatory; it corresponds to the former SSD1 element *prodText* and can be used to provide an example and short explanation of the food sample tested. It should be provided if it is considered that the textual description of the selected code from the MTX catalogue is insufficient, the FoodEx2 code is complex and the data provider is unsure as to whether the correct codes have been selected, or if there are no suitable codes to describe the item sampled. If *sampMatText* is reported, then it must be reported with the same free text for all single determinations belonging to the same sample (i.e. for the same *sampId* code).

4.12. origCountry - Country of origin of the sample taken (E.04)

This data element specifies the origin of the food product analysed. As for the SSD1 reporting, also for the SSD2 coding, the information to be reported in this data element is mandatory and shall be selected from the catalogue COUNTRY. For the pesticide data collection, the selectable codes are provided in the Catalogue Browser from the 'pestCountry' hierarchy. All codes of this catalogue except 'AA', 'EU', 'XC', 'XD' and 'XE' are valid for this data element. If it is not possible to identify the country of origin, the most appropriate code to be selected is 'XX' (i.e. 'Unknown').

In the past, EFSA noted that in some cases data providers used the code of the country where the product was packed instead of the code of the country where the food was produced (e.g. rice with as country of origin Iceland). This should be avoided; reporting countries are encouraged to identify the origin of the product; this is particularly true for unprocessed (raw) food products and for cases where the MRL is exceeding. Additional information on the country of processing can be reported on a voluntarily basis in the relevant data element 'country of food processing' (*procCountry*, SSD2 data element E.08 and COUNTRY catalogue).

4.13. sampMatInfo - Additional information on the matrix sampled (E.10)

This compound field can be used to report additional information and comments about the matrix sampled depending on the specific requirements of the different data collection domains. For the pesticide monitoring data collection, this element can be used to provide e.g. the sample production and expiry dates. This data element can be used to report any piece of information as it was previously done in SSD1 by means of the former data element *prodCom* (SSD1 element S.21). If *sampMatInfo* is reported, then it must be reported with the same free text for all single determinations belonging to the same sample.

In case the data provided to EFSA contains commercially sensitive information and/or personal data, be aware of the information reported in footnote (19); thus, when submitting data to EFSA, the data providers should be acquainted with the stringent transparency obligations by which EFSA is bound to disclose the information provided.

4.14. sampAnId - Sample analysed identification code (F.01)

The information provided for this data element is not mandatory in the context of the pesticide monitoring data collection. In fact, each 'sample analysed' contains an alphanumeric identification code. Since the 'analysed sample section' (Group F of the SSD2 data elements; see Table 1) is not

needed for all data collection domains (for e.g. it is not needed in the pesticide residue area) in order to simplify the population of the data model, this element will be assumed to have the same value as the 'sample taken identification code' (element D.01 *sampId*, see also section 4.6) unless otherwise populated. Where multiple results corresponding to different parameters are reported for the same 'sample analysed', the 'unique sample identification number' must be maintained for the 'sample analysed' in all transmissions.

4.15. **analysisY - Year of analysis (F.03), analysisM - Month of analysis (F.04) and analysisD - Day of analysis (F.05)**

As for SSD1 data reporting, only the year of analysis (*analysisY*, F.03) is mandatory. No changes have been brought to the reporting of the date of analysis compared to SSD1.

4.16. **labId – Laboratory identification code (J.01)**

In comparison to the SSD1, the data element name to indicate the laboratory code has changed, but its meaning was not affected. Thus, this data element corresponds to the former SSD1 element *labCode* (L.01).

The reporting of the *labId* is mandatory for the pesticide monitoring. A unique code to identify each laboratory providing laboratory results should be reported here (i.e. the national laboratory code). This code should be reported consistently for all data transmissions. This code should also be used when providing information on participation in proficiency tests in the National Summary Report, as appropriate.

4.17. **labAccred – Laboratory accreditation (J.02)**

This mandatory element indicates whether the laboratories performing the analysis have been accredited as required in Article 12 of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004. For pesticide monitoring, only two codes from the LABACC catalogue may be used (see Table 120). So, no changes have been introduced in this data element in the SSD2.

Table 12 Codes to be used to describe the laboratory accreditation status (LABACC catalogue)

Element value	Code description	Note
L001A	Accredited	Accredited according to ISO/IEC 17025 for pesticides analysis.
L003A	None	For results generated by laboratories not or not yet accredited according to ISO/IEC 17025 for pesticide residues (e.g. When the laboratory is awaiting the final audit form of the accreditation body.)

4.18. **paramType - Type of parameter (K.01)**

The name and meaning of this SSD variable has not changed in SSD2 in comparison to SSD1 and the related catalogue has remained unchanged. Therefore, the reader is recommended to read section 5.5 of the EFSA Guidance on the use of SSD1 for the coding of the 2018 pesticide residues monitoring data (EFSA, 2019b) and the associated examples.

For the pesticide monitoring data collection, an official and agreed classification of the type of pesticide enforcement residue definitions is not available. However, these residue definitions can be broadly classified in:

- 'Simple': residue definitions that contain only the parent compound or one single component/compound;
- 'Multicomponent': residue definitions that comprise more than one component/compound, as for example the parent compound and one or more metabolites.

Official control laboratories are not always in the position to analyse the entire multicomponent legal residue definitions, as required by Regulation (EC) No 396/2005, as for example all metabolites or degradation products that are part of the definition because the analytical standards for metabolites are not commercially available. For the correct interpretation of the analytical results submitted to EFSA, in the framework of pesticide data collection, it is essential to know whether a sample was analysed for all components of the legal residue definition or not. Thus, the mandatory data element *paramType* was introduced to this scope and a specific catalogue is available for the correct coding (PARAMTYP catalogue). Table 13 explains the codes from the PARAMTYP catalogue that can be used to describe the different *paramType* options.

Table 13 Codes to be used to describe the type of parameter (PARAMTYP catalogue)

Code value	Code description	Note
P005A	Full legal residue definition analysed for	This code is to be selected when the analytical measurement fully complies with the legal Residue Definition (RD), for both Simple residue definitions or for Multicomponent residue definitions, <u>where the sample was analysed for all components</u> .
P004A	Sum based on subset	This code must be selected only when the analytical measurement refers to a RD AND where <u>not all components have been analysed for</u> . P004A is not appropriate for reporting the results concerning Simple RD.
P002A	Part of a sum	This code is to be selected for the reporting of a single component included in a Multicomponent RD. Results coded with P002A will normally not be included in the data analysis presented in the EU Report on pesticide residues as the MRL compliance (see data analysis presented in Section 2 and 3 of the 2017 report (EFSA, 2018)). However, for specific data analysis (e.g. for refined consumer's intake calculations) the results labelled with P002A might be used by EFSA. For the EU-coordinated control programme results for Multicomponent RD, the data providers shall report the analysis results for the analytes that are part of the residue definition separately (with the code P002A), as far as they are measured individually. Finally, for the single component being part of Multicomponent RD (reported with P002A), the result should be expressed in mg/kg for the analytes (without expressing it as defined in the RD). The code P002A can be also used to report safeners and synergists.

4.19. paramCode - Coded description of the parameter (K.02)

The name and meaning of this SSD variable has not changed in SSD2 in comparison to SSD1.

This mandatory data element is used to describe the substance(s) analysed for which the measured result is reported. The PARAM catalogue has been developed for coding this variable; it contains the codes for the legal residue definitions as defined in Regulation (EC) No 396/2005, but also codes for other type of residues than pesticides (from veterinary medicinal products, food and feed additives, flavourings, nutrients or contaminants, etc.), or codes for substances that are part of the legal residue definition for pesticides' residues. In order to select the codes needed, please choose only one of the codes listed under the specific 'pestParam' hierarchy in the PARAM Catalogue Browser.

Please note that for pesticide legal residue definitions that changed during the monitoring year only one of the residue definitions (*paramCode*) may be selected for the same sample, the one considered

by the data provider as the applicable. This means that only one combination of *paramCode/sampId* for the same sample is acceptable.

It is important to recall that the following three PARAM codes are not selectable for any data collection: RF-XXXX-XXX-XXX='Not in list', RF-XXXX-XXX-X01='Unknown' and RF-XXXX-XXX-X02='Unspecified'.

4.19.1. The MatrixTool

The choice of the correct *paramCode* for a given combination of pesticide residue definition/food analysed can also be done by consulting the EFSA supporting tool named MatrixTool, which encompasses all the valid, plausible triple combinations of *paramCode/paramType* specific for the pesticide residues monitoring data collection and for each food item as per Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 MRL food classification. Considering that the pesticide MRL food classification only refers to unprocessed food samples, the MatrixTool (for the time being) only provides the combinations of the *paramCode/paramType* linked to the past SSD1 food catalogue (MATRIX catalogue). The MatrixTool is not included in this guidance document but is provided separately as an Excel file. Further important explanation on the structure and use of the MatrixTool can be found in section 5.3 of the EFSA Guidance on the use of the SSD1 for the coding of the 2018 pesticide residues monitoring data (EFSA, 2019b).

4.20. resId – Result identification code (M.01)

This element contains the unique identification number of an analytical result (i.e. the single analytical determination) in the transmitted file, i.e. no changes have been introduced while moving from SSD1 to SSD2. This element is mandatory for the pesticide monitoring data collection; it will be used by EFSA also during the data validation process as reference for error messages and/or to identify records to be deleted or replaced.

4.21. resUnit - Result unit (M.03)

For the pesticide data collection, the only code accepted from the UNIT catalogue is G061A (Milligram/kilogram), for both solid and liquid samples. No changes have been introduced with the SSD2 in the interpretation and use of the information to be reported in this SSD variable. Thus, the reporting of the result unit remains mandatory.

4.22. resLOQ - Result LOQ (M.05)

This data element is mandatory also for the SSD2 reporting. The data provider must report the Limit of Quantification (LOQ) of the analytical method used to analyse the sample described and the combination of the data elements *sampMatCode* for the parameter described in the *paramCode*. The numerical LOQ (expressed always as mg/kg) must be provided for each analytical determination. The same is applicable for screening methods. Since there are no changes in the interpretation and use of this piece of information, the reader is strongly invited to read section 5.12 of the EFSA Guidance on the use of the SSD1 for the coding of the 2018 pesticide residues monitoring data (EFSA, 2019b). However, it should be highlighted that, starting from the 2018 pesticide monitoring data collection, new BRs have been set-up on the *resLOQ* in case of Multicomponent residue definitions. Please be aware of this and read more information on the topic in the document above linked and/or read the full list of BRs applicable for both the SSD1 and SSD2 reporting of the 2018 pesticide monitoring data (documents provided separately). The new approach is to avoid the issues created by some domains previously using a false value of '99999' in *resLOQ* when the summed LOQ was not possible.

In the SANCO document for pesticides (SANCO/12574/2014 rev.5)²⁴, some provisions for reporting the 'resLOQ' according to the residue definition type are provided. For 'Multicomponent' pesticide residue definitions, EFSA requests to report the individual LOQ for each component of that residue definition and a summed LOQ, which is calculated by the reporting country. In case the reporting country cannot provide to EFSA the summed LOQ, the data providers need to flag it by returning the appropriate value in the element 4.27 'Not summed'. (See also paragraph 4.27 on

²⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/plant/docs/pesticides_mrl_guidelines_wrkdoc_12574.pdf

resInfo.notSummed). Business rules will be introduced to ensure that *resLOQ* can only be null where *resInfo.notSummed* = 'Y'.

4.23. *resVal* – Result value (M.10)

The data element *resVal* is a mandatory field only if the pesticide analysed (*paramCode*) was found in concentrations at or exceeding the LOQ (i.e. if the *resType* code is equal to 'VAL'; please refer also to see Section 4.26 on *resType*). It should be left blank for determinations lower than the *resLOQ* (i.e. if the *resType* code is equal to 'LOQ').

There are no differences in the use of this data element from SSD1 to SSD2. The numerical value reported for this variable should be expressed in the unit indicated for the *resUnit* variable (i.e. in mg/kg).

On a general basis, the results for processed food products should be reported for the sample analysed, i.e. the processed product, without any recalculation of the result of the unprocessed product. The same applies to the two data elements *resLOQ* and *resLOD*.

It should be highlighted that duplicate results (i.e. results of replicate analysis of the same sample) are not accepted. If the same sample was analysed (same test portion) by means of different analytical methods, the result derived with the most accurate or reliable analysis is to be reported where samples were analysed with equally accurate techniques, the mean value should be reported. The mean result shall also be reported where different subsamples were analysed (EC, 2013).

If a sample was analysed with screening methods, the data element *resVal* should be left blank since for screening methods only negative results are accepted (results below the LOQ, see also Section 4.26).

4.24. *resValRec* – Result value recovery rate (M.11)

The data element is mandatory only if the residue result reported in the field *resVal* was adjusted for recovery ('Y' in the field *resValRecCorr*); in this case the recovery obtained with the method validation (expressed as percentage of the recovery, e.g. for 65 for 65 % recovery) used to recalculate the result is to be reported.

4.25. *resQualValue* - Result qualitative value (M.15)

This data element is mandatory only under certain conditions and can be used only in case of qualitative screening results (i.e. for confirmatory results or quantifiable results *resQualValue* should not be reported). In case of screening results the reported *resType*='BIN' and then *resQualValue* must be reported with the value 'NEG'.

4.26. *resType* – Type of result (M.16)

This data element is mandatory in SSD2 as it was in SSD1; its meaning and use has not changed.

In the frame of the pesticide monitoring reporting, only four codes are selectable for the type of result (VALTYP catalogue). The description of the codes and the cases to use them can be found in Table 14.

Table 14 Type of result codes (VALTYP catalogue) selectable for the pesticide residue data coding

Code value	Code description	Note
VAL	Numerical Value	If the residue specified in the field <i>paramCode</i> was quantified at or above the LOQ, the data element must be completed with the code 'VAL'. Thus, the numerical value of determination reported in the data element <i>resVal</i> is to be equal or greater than the LOQ of the analytical method reported in the data element <i>resLOQ</i> .
LOQ	Non Quantified Value (<LOQ)	If the measured residue concentration was below the LOQ, then the element <i>resType</i> shall be completed with the code 'LOQ'. In this case, the data element <i>resVal</i> should be left blank and the data element <i>resLOQ</i> should be used to report the numerical value of the Limit of

Code value	Code description	Note
		Quantification.
LOD	Non Detected Value (<LOD)	If the residue is not detected, the element <i>resType</i> shall be completed with the code 'LOD'. In this case, the data element <i>resVal</i> should be left blank and the data element <i>resLOD</i> should be used to report the numerical value of the Limit of detection.
BIN	Qualitative Value (Binary)	If a sample was analysed with a screening method and the result was below the LOQ, the result type is to be labelled with BIN. In this case, the data element <i>resVal</i> should be left blank. In the field <i>resLOQ</i> the reporting value of the LOQ of the screening method (expressed in mg/kg) should be reported.

4.27. *resInfo.notSummed* – summed LOQ (M.20)

For the pesticide residue data collection, the compound element 'notSummed' is optional and it should be used to flag to EFSA if the LOQ has been already calculated for a Multicomponent Residue Definition analytical results by the data providers as a 'summed LOQ' or not. The only reportable 'values' for this element are: 'Y' (Yes), 'N' (No) or a blank/null value:

- In case the *notSummed* is left **blank/null**, EFSA will interpret it as 'N' (No).
- If the reporting country will not report the 'summed LOQ', then *resLOQ* can be left null if *paramType* = P005A or P004A and *resInfo.notSummed* is set to 'Y'. In this case, upon data submission to EFSA, the *resLOQ* will be calculated by EFSA based on the single LOQ values reported for the individual components of the residue definition with a *paramType*=P002A'. For this reason, the reporting of the *resLOQ* for records with *paramType*=P002A is mandatory. Business Rules will be introduced to ensure that *resLOQ* can only be NULL where *resInfo.notSummed*=~Y'.

For more details on this topic see also section 4.22 on the *resLOQ* data element.

4.28. *evalLowLimit* – Limit for the result evaluation (N.01)

This data element was already encompassed by SSD1 (*resLegalLimit*, Legal limit for the result). In SSD2, the name has changed, however, no changes in its use is foreseen for the pesticide residues coding. Thus, the variable in SSD2 specifies the source of the legal limit used for compliance check (i.e. the legal limit applicable at the time of sampling). The reporting of this data element is mandatory only for the results of food/pesticide combinations for which the EU MRL has changed in the course of the year and/or in the case that for the same combination a valid legal limit (numerically different from the pesticide MRL) exists under the veterinary drug residues legislation, if the food tested was 'unprocessed' and only if the value in the data element *resType* is equal to a 'Numerical value' (VAL). If the data element is left blank in this situation, an error message will be triggered. Thus, this data element is compulsory only in a limited number of instances.

4.29. *evalCode* – Evaluation of the result (N.04)

This SSD2 data element corresponds to the former SSD1 variable *resEvaluation*. Despite the change in its name, there are no changes in its use and coding; thus, as in SSD1 this element provides information about the conclusion of the reporting country on the results reported in the field *resVal*, in the case it is considered as exceeding the legal limit (e.g. pesticide MRL) that was applicable to the tested sample. The SSD catalogue associated to the *evalCode* is still the RESEVAL.

The only codes selectable in the area of pesticide residue monitoring for the reporting of this mandatory data element are listed in Table 15.

Table 15 Codes from the RESVAL catalogue to be used for describing MRL compliance of a result (*evalCode*).

Code value	Code description	Note
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Code value	Code description	Note
J002A	≤ maximum permissible quantities	This code must be used if (i) the residue concentration measured in the sample and reported in the data element <i>resVal</i> was numerically below or at the MRL applicable for this determination (i.e. the MRL reported in <i>evalLowLimit</i>) or (ii) the residue concentration measured in the sample is reported in the data element <i>resType</i> as LOQ, LOD or BIN.
J003A	> maximum permissible quantities	This code is to be used when the residue concentration measured in the sample and reported in the data element <i>resVal</i> was found to clearly exceeding the legal limit (considering the analytical measurement uncertainty).
J031A	Compliant due to measurement uncertainty	This code is to be used when the residue concentration measured in the sample and reported in the data element <i>resVal</i> was found to numerically exceeding the legal limit, but for which no legal sanctions were imposed considering the measurement uncertainty.
J029A	Result not evaluated	To be used for results for which the reporting country did not assess the compliance/non-compliance, e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for products for which no EU nor national MRLs are in place (e.g. feed, fish, composite food), or • for substances for which no EU or national MRLs are in place (e.g. synergists), or • for determinations that are labelled with P002A in the data element <i>paramType</i>, or • if the analytical method was not sensitive enough to check MRL compliance (LOQ>MRL).

The reader is invited to consult the examples on this topic, which are provided in section 5.24 of the EFSA Guidance on the use of the SSD1 for the coding of the 2018 pesticide residues monitoring data.

References

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- European Commission, 2014. Working document on the summing up of LOQs in case of complex residue definitions. SANCO/12574/2014. Document available at: https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/plant/docs/pesticides_mrl_guidelines_wrkdoc_12574.pdf
- European Commission, 2017. Guidance document on analytical quality control and validation procedures for pesticide residues analysis in food and feed. SANCO/11813/2017.

Useful supporting material

- EFSA's Catalogue browser user guide: <https://zenodo.org/record/1407103#.XIkl4hKiUn>
- FoodEx2 browser draft user guide: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/assets/BrowsingToolInstruction.pdf>
- Web link to download the Catalogue Browser: <https://github.com/openefsa/catalogue-browser/wiki>
- Two on-line training/tutorials on the FoodEx2 classification system and practical guidance on its use are available on the EFSA webpage: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/events/event/180926>

Abbreviations

BIN	Qualitative Value (Binary)
BR	Business Rule
DCF	Data Collection Framework
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EURL	European Reference Laboratory
EU	European Union
FoodEx2	EFSA's food classification and description system
ICT	Interpreting and Checking Tool
LOD	Analytical Limit of Determination
LOQ	Analytical Limit of Quantification
MRL	Maximum Residue Level
MTX	FoodEx2 Matrix catalogue
RASFF	Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed
RD	Residue definition
RPC	Raw Primary Commodity
SSD1	Standard Sample Description (ver. 1)
SSD2	Standard Sample Description (ver. 2)
VAL	Numerical value

Appendix A – FoodEx2 coding for the food items under the 2018 EU Co-ordinated monitoring programme

In the table below the food commodities included in the 2018 EU co-ordinated monitoring programme are listed along with the appropriate SSD codes for the food product (*sampMatCode*, E.02), sampling strategy (*sampStrategy*, B.03), programme legal reference (*progLegalRef*, B.02) and type of sampling programme (*progType*, B.04).

Food product as per 2018 EUCP Regulation	<i>sampMatCode</i> (MTX) code and its description	F28 'Process' facets ²⁵ (MTX) code and description	<i>progLegalRef</i> (LEGREF) code	<i>SampStrategy</i> (SAMPSTR) code	<i>progType</i> (SRCTYP) code	Note on the food product tested
Grapefruits	A01CY (Grapefruits)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) A07KQ (Freezing)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	Whole product after removal of the stem
Table grapes	A01DX (Table grapes)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) A07KQ (Freezing)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	Whole product after removal of the caps, crowns and stems
Bananas	A01LC (Common banana)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) A07KQ (Freezing)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	Whole product after removal of the stem
Sweet peppers/bell peppers	A00JA (Sweet peppers)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) A07KQ (Freezing)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	Whole product after removal of the stem
Aubergines/eggplants	A00JD (Aubergines)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) A07KQ (Freezing)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	Whole product after removal of the stem
Melons	A00KF (Melons)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) A07KQ (Freezing)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	Whole product after removal of the stem
Broccoli	A00FN (Broccoli)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) A07KQ (Freezing)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	Whole product after removal of roots and decayed leaves
Cultivated fungi	A00TQ (Common mushrooms)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) A07KQ (Freezing)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	Whole product after removal of soil or growing medium
Virgin olive oil	A036Q (Olive oil, virgin or extra-virgin)	The MTX code A036Q already includes the implicit facet F28 'Process Oil production - mechanical cold' (MTX code A0C06) attached to the base term code 'Olives for oil production' (A016M); thus, the facet F28 in this case does not need to be added ²⁶ .	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	If no specific oil processing factor is available, a default factor of 5 may be applied for fat soluble substances, considering an olive oil production standard yield of 20% of the olive harvest; for non-fat soluble substances a default oil processing factor of 1 may be used. Member States are requested to report the processing factors used in the 'National Summary report'.

²⁵ In case the facet 'Process' is not reported by the data provider, EFSA will assume the 'Unprocessed' code A0C0S as the applicable one. For the MTX codes that already contain implicit Process facet (e.g. in case of olive oil), no Process code should be add.

²⁶ In the remote case the virgin olive oil was produced by a warm pressing, this should be needing to explicitly be reported by using the facet F28 code for 'Oil production mechanical warm' (code A0C08).

Food product as per 2018 EUCP Regulation	sampMatCode (MTX) code and its description	F28 'Process' facets ²⁵ (MTX) code and description	progLegalRef (LEGREF) code	SampStrategy (SAMPSTR) code	progType (SRCTYP) code	Note on the food product tested
Wheat grains	A001N (Common wheat grain)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	If not enough samples of wheat grains are available, also wholemeal/unprocessed wheat flour can be analysed and a processing factor shall be reported.
	A004B (Wheat wholemeal flour)	The MTX code A004B already contains the implicit facet Process code A0C0A (Grain milling – flours production) N027A	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	In this case, the MTX code A004B for wholemeal flour should be used. If no specific processing factors are available, a default factor of 1 may be applied.
Fat (bovine)	A01TY (Cattle fresh fat tissue)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) A07KQ (Freezing)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	Whole product
Eggs (chicken)	A031G (Hen eggs)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) A07KQ (Freezing)	N027A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	Whole eggs without the shell shall be analysed
Processed cereal-based foods for infants and young children	A03QX (Processed cereal-based food for infants and young children)	A0C0R (‘Processed’, see also the note in the last column)	N028A	ST10A/ST20A	K009A/K018A	When ‘Processed cereal-based foods for infants and young children’ samples are reported with the MTX code A0C0R or with one of its sub-codes, the EFSA mapping rules will automatically assume the samples as ‘Processed’, as per EU legislation. Therefore, for the pesticide data collection there is no need to provide an explicit F28 Process facet.

Appendix B – FoodEx2 coding for the food items under Regulation (EC) No 669/2009

In the table below the food commodities and the countries covered by the Regulation (EC) No 669/2009 and its amendments relevant for the 2018 control year are listed along with the product code (*sampMatCode*, E.02), country of origin of the product (*origCountry*, E.04), sampling strategy (*sampStrategy*, B.03) and the programme type (*progType*, B.04).

Food to be analysed ^(a)	Note ²⁷	MRL food group/subgroup according to Reg (EC) No 396/2005	<i>sampMatCode</i> (MTX) code and description	F28 'Process' facets ²⁸ (MTX) code and description	Country of origin	<i>SampStrategy</i> (SAMPSTR) code	<i>origCountry</i> (CTRY) code	<i>progType</i> (SRCTYP) code	Checks (%) ^(b)
Pineapples		Pineapples	A01LP (Pineapples)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	Benin	ST30A	BJ	K019A	10-20
Chinese celery (<i>Apium graveolens</i>)		Celery leaves	A00XA (Celery leaves)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	Cambodia	ST30A	KH	K019A	50
Yardlong beans (<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> spp. <i>sesquipedalis</i> , <i>vigna unguiculata</i> spp. <i>unguiculata</i>)		Beans (with pods)	A00PF (Yardlong beans (with pods))	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Cambodia	ST30A	KH	K019A	50
Brassica oleracea (other edible Brassica, 'Chinese Broccoli')	Chinese Broccoli	Broccoli	A00FQ (Chinese broccoli)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	China	ST30A	CN	K019A	0-20
Goji berries (wolfberries) (<i>Lycium barbarum</i> L.)	NEW entry in 2018	Tomatoes	A0DMR (Wolfberries)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or For dried goji berries: A00ZQ#F27.A0DMR (corresponding to 'Dried vegetables' and 'Wolfberries')	China	ST30A	CN	K019A	0-10
Tea	Tea, whether or not flavoured	Tea	A04KK or one of its 4 children codes	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	China	ST30A	CN	K019A	10
Peppers (sweet and other than sweet (<i>Capsicum</i> spp.))	Sweet peppers	Sweet peppers/bell peppers	A00JA (Sweet peppers)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Dominican Republic	ST30A	DO	K019A	20
Peppers (sweet and other than sweet (<i>Capsicum</i> spp.))	Chili peppers	Sweet peppers/bell	A00JB (Chili peppers)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Dominican Republic	ST30A	DO	K019A	20

²⁷ Note on the food to be analysed according to Regulation (EU) No 669/2009.

²⁸ In case the facet 'Process' is not reported by the data provider, EFSA will assume the Unprocessed code A0C0S as the applicable one. For the MTX codes that already contain implicit Process facet (e.g. in case of olive oil), no Process code should be add.

Food to be analysed ^(a)	Note ²⁷	MRL food group/subgroup according to Reg (EC) No 396/2005	sampMatCode (MTX) code and description	F28 'Process' facets ²⁸ (MTX) code and description	Country of origin	SampStrategy (SAMPSTR) code	origCountry (CTRY) code	progType (SRCTYP) code	Checks (%) ^(b)
		peppers							
Yardlong beans (<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> spp. <i>sesquipedalis</i>)		Beans (with pods)	A00PF (Yardlong beans (with pods))	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Dominican Republic	ST30A	DO	K019A	20
Peppers (sweet and other than sweet (<i>Capsicum</i> spp.))	Sweet peppers	Sweet peppers/bell peppers	A00JA (Sweet peppers)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Egypt	ST30A	EG	K019A	10
Peppers (sweet and other than sweet (<i>Capsicum</i> spp.))	Chili peppers	Sweet peppers/bell peppers	A00JB (Chili peppers)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Egypt	ST30A	EG	K019A	10
Strawberries		Strawberries	A01EA (Strawberries)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or	Egypt	ST30A	EG	K019A	0-10
Curry leaves (<i>bergera/Murraya koenigii</i>)	NEW entry in 2018	Laurel/bay leaves	A00XG (Curry leaves)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing) or For dried curry leaves: A016T#F27.A00XG (corresponding to 'dried herbs' and 'curry leaves')	India	ST30A	IN	K019A	0-20
Okra	NEW entry in 2018	Okra, lady's fingers	A00JF (Okra)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	India	ST30A	IN	K019A	0-10
Peppers (other than sweet) (<i>Capsicum</i> spp.)	Chili peppers NEW entry in 2018	Sweet peppers/bell peppers	A00JB (Chili peppers)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	India	ST30A	IN	K019A	10
Peas with pods (unshelled)		Peas (with pods)	A00PX (Peas (with pods) and similar)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	Kenya	ST30A	KE	K019A	0-5
Peppers (other than sweet) (<i>Capsicum</i> spp.)	Chili peppers NEW entry in 2018	Sweet peppers/bell peppers	A00JB (Chili peppers)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Pakistan	ST30A	PK	K019A	10
Peppers (other than sweet) (<i>Capsicum</i> spp.)	Chili peppers	Sweet peppers/bell peppers	A00JB (Chili peppers)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Thailand	ST30A	TH	K019A	10
Yardlong beans (<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> spp. <i>sesquipedalis</i> , <i>vigna unguiculata</i>)		Beans (with pods)	A00PF (Yardlong beans (with pods))	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Thailand	ST30A	TH	K019A	0-20

Food to be analysed ^(a)	Note ²⁷	MRL food group/subgroup according to Reg (EC) No 396/2005	sampMatCode (MTX) code and description	F28 'Process' facets ²⁸ (MTX) code and description	Country of origin	SampStrategy (SAMPSTR) code	origCountry (CTRY) code	progType (SRCTYP) code	Checks (%) ^(b)
spp. unguiculata)									
Lemons		Lemons	A01BY (Lemons)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or For dried lemons: A01MA#F27.A01BY (corresponding to 'Dried fruit' and 'lemons')	Turkey	ST30A	TR	K019A	10-20
Pomegranates		Granate apples/Pomegranate	A01LH (Granate apples)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	Turkey	ST30A	TR	K019A	10-20
Sweet peppers (Capsicum annum)	Sweet peppers	Sweet peppers/bell peppers	A00JA (Sweet peppers)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Turkey	ST30A	TR	K019A	10
Vine leaves		Grape leaves and similar species	A00NB (Grape leaves)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A0C0R (Processed)	Turkey	ST30A	TR	K019A	20-50
Aubergines (Solanum melongena) or Ethiopian eggplant (Solanum aethiopicum)	NEW entry in 2018	Aubergines/eggplants	A00JD (Aubergines) A0DMF (Ethiopian eggplants)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing) A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Uganda	ST30A	UG	K019A	0-20
Basil (holy, sweet)		Basil	A0DHD (Holy basil)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	Viet Nam	ST30A	VN	K019A	50
Coriander leaves		Celery leaves	A00XF (Coriander leaves)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	Viet Nam	ST30A	VN	K019A	50
Mint		Basil	A00YB (Peppermint)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	Viet Nam	ST30A	VN	K019A	50
Okra		Okra, lady's fingers	A00JF (Okra)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Viet Nam	ST30A	VN	K019A	50
Parsley		Parsley	A00YE (Parsley)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	Viet Nam	ST30A	VN	K019A	50
Peppers (other than sweet) (Capsicum spp.)	Chili peppers	Sweet peppers/bell peppers	A00JB (Chili peppers)	A0C0S (Unprocessed) or A07KQ (Freezing)	Viet Nam	ST30A	VN	K019A	50

Food to be analysed^(a)	Note²⁷	MRL food group/subgroup according to Reg (EC) No 396/2005	sampMatCode (MTX) code and description	F28 'Process' facets²⁸ (MTX) code and description	Country of origin	SampStrategy (SAMPSTR) code	origCountry (CTRY) code	progType (SRCTYP) code	Checks (%)^(b)
Pitahaya (dragon fruit)		Prickly pear (cactus fruit)	A0DQS (Pitayas)	A0C0S (Unprocessed)	Viet Nam	ST30A	VN	K019A	10

(a) Food as described in one of the implementing regulations of Regulation (EU) No 669/2009.

(b) Frequency of checks according to Regulation (EC) No 669/2009 and its amendments, whose provisions were applicable in 2018.